

Degree Project in Electrical Engineering (Nanotechnology)

Second Cycle 30 Credits

In Vitro Organoid Electrophysiology Recording Platform

Integrating Hydrodynamic Trapping Microfluidics,
Microelectrode Arrays, Front-end Electronics, and Offline Signal
Processing for Dynamic Monitoring of Extracellular Activities in
Pancreatic Islets

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Abstract

Type I diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disorder affecting the insulin-producing beta cells of the islets of Langerhans, disrupting the glucose homeostasis regulatory system. Nowadays, islet transplantation is one of the anticipated treatments to revive the endocrinal function by injecting isolated pancreatic islets from a deceased donor into the patient's liver's portal vein. Regardless of the promising aspect, the main issue prior to transplantation is the inconsistent quality and low percentage of functioning islets post-transplantation. Therefore, a rapid islet functionality test with minimal complicated operation becomes necessary to tackle the pre-transplantation issue. This project revolves around the end-to-end development of an electrophysiology recording platform to monitor extracellular activities in murine pancreatic islets. A microfluidic perfusion system with hydrodynamic trapping is integrated with planar gold microelectrode arrays (MEA) as the preliminary device directly interfacing the islets. The design and fabrication of both the microfluidics and electrode devices, as well as in-house front-end electronics with analog filters and amplifiers tailored to capture the microvolt-scale signals, covered most of the project. Offline digital processing was performed in Python to analyse the recorded signals further. As a result, the complete platform and recording setup have been fully integrated, with successful islet trapping on top of electrodes and front-end electronics with 220x voltage gain and 0.1-3000 Hz bandwidth to record extracellular electrophysiology signals from intact pancreatic islets. While the current preliminary electrophysiology recordings are still quite inconclusive and require further validation, the project serves as a starting point in developing devices for extracellular electrophysiology measurement, which has not commonly been investigated specifically in pancreatic islets, and enables further exploration in the field.

Keywords

Glucose-stimulated insulin response, hydrodynamic trapping, insulin secretion, islets of Langerhans, microelectrode array (MEA), microfluidics

Sammanfattning

Typ I-diabetes (T1D) är en autoimmun sjukdom som påverkar de insulinproducerande betacellerna på de Langerhanska öarna och stör det reglerande systemet för glukoshomeostas. Nuförtiden är ötransplantation en av de förväntade behandlingarna för att återuppliva den endokrina funktionen genom att injicera isolerade pankreasöar från en avliden donator i patientens levers portven. Oavsett den lovande aspekten är huvudfrågan före transplantation den inkonsekventa kvaliteten och låga andelen fungerande öar efter transplantationen. Därför blir ett snabbt funktionstest av öar med minimalt komplicerad operation nödvändigt för att ta itu med problemet före transplantation. Detta projekt kretsar kring end-to-end utveckling av en elektrofysiologisk inspelningsplattform för att övervaka extracellulära aktiviteter i murina pankreatiska öar. Ett mikrofluidiskt perfusionssystem med hydrodynamisk infångning är integrerat med plana guldmikroelektrodarrayer (MEA) som den preliminära enheten som direkt gränsar till öarna. Designen och tillverkningen av både mikrofluidik och elektrodenheter, såväl som intern front-end-elektronik med analoga filter och förstärkare skräddarsydda för att fånga signalerna i mikrovoltskala, täckte större delen av projektet. Offline digital bearbetning utfördes i Python för att analysera de inspelade signalerna ytterligare. Som ett resultat har den kompletta plattformen och inspelningsuppsättningen integrerats helt, med lyckad ö-infångning ovanpå elektroder och front-end-elektronik med 220x spänningsförstärkning och 0,1-3000 Hz för att registrera extracellulära elektrofysiologiska signaler från intakta pankreatiska öar. Medan de nuvarande preliminära elektrofysiologiska inspelningarna fortfarande är ganska ofullständiga och kräver ytterligare validering, fungerar projektet som en utgångspunkt för att utveckla enheter för extracellulär elektrofysiologisk mätning, som inte vanligtvis har undersökts specifikt i pankreasöar, och möjliggör ytterligare utforskning inom området.

Nyckelord

Glukosstimulerad insulinreaktion, hydrodynamisk fångst, insulinutsöndring, Langerhanska öar, mikroelektrod uppsättningar, mikrofluidik

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The project aims to develop a platform to perform rapid pancreatic islet functionality tests on single-islet resolution with minimal complicated operation. The chapter starts by describing the specific issue that would be addressed, followed by the detailed context of the issue, project purposes and goals, research methodology, delimitations, and finally, the thesis outline structure.

1.1 Background

Type I diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disorder where the immune system attacks the insulin-producing beta cells of the islets of Langerhans. On the other hand, Type 2 Diabetes (T2D) is caused by insufficient functional beta cells due to prolonged hyperglycemia. Both forms of diabetes disrupt the glucose homeostasis regulatory system and can lead to severe complications, affecting millions worldwide. [1]

Islet allotransplantation is one of the anticipated treatments for diabetes, especially in T1D patients, with the ability to restore the endocrinal function of maintaining normoglycemia. [2] The procedure involves injecting pancreatic islets isolated from a deceased donor into the patient's liver's portal vein. [3] Regardless of the promising aspect, the method is hindered by the inconsistent islet quality and the high percentage of dismissed islets due to the islet graft failure-associated issues. [4] Thus, to ensure the success of the transplantation procedure, it is crucial to establish proper pre-transplantation islet quality monitoring to sort out non-functioning islets and acquire a high throughput of functioning islets.

Given the need, many options for different islet functionality assessments exist nowadays. One of the most utilised islet functionality assessments is the gold standard quantification of glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) through enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA). The challenge of this method is the need for trained personnel, besides the tedious and time-consuming process. [5, 6] Another prevalent islet potency assessment is in vivo potency assays to predict islet graft function post-transplantation, conducted by transplanting human pancreatic islets to immunodeficient nude mice. [4, 7] While the method may provide valuable insights into post-transplantation islet function, the evaluation technique is highly time-consuming, as it often requires several weeks to yield any result. Due to those challenges, most currently available approaches are impractical for time-sensitive pre-transplantation assessment. For that reason, a rapid islet potency test with minimal operation becomes necessary to tackle the issue.

Many researchers have explored the miniaturisation of islet functionality assessment in a microphysiological system to address the problem. [6, 8, 9] Although it is one of the most employed methods, detecting insulin secreted from the GSIS tests requires temporal resolution verification to ensure the produced insulin is not diluted by the medium perfusion, which adds more complexity to the system. Placing the insulin sensors in close proximity to the islets utilising certain trapping mechanisms might enhance the byproduct detection. However, the stability and selectivity issues still remain, considering the other biomolecules secreted along with the continuous perfusion that could interfere with the reading. Therefore, it highlights the need for a more straightforward, reliable method for assessing islet functionality that focuses on the insulin secretion process rather than its byproducts to provide a more representative approach.

Considering the challenges, assessing the insulin-releasing function directly through extracellular electrophysiology offers several compelling benefits. The approach relies on monitoring electrical activities excited following the exchange of ion channels in the plasma membrane corresponding to the glucose-dependent insulin secretion. [10, 11]. The technique provides the ability to continuously monitor single-islet level response to glucose stimuli in real-time and with a very high temporal resolution compared to the other conventional methods. [12, 13] While cytoplasmic calcium imaging techniques also provide direct observation of the insulin secretion process, extracellular electrophysiology offers a label-free approach that is more physiologically

relevant and preferable for translational research involving human islets. Calcium imaging often requires the transgenic islets engineered to express fluorescent calcium indicators such as GCaMP3, or adding fluorescent labels to the normal islet. Using a label-free approach eliminates potential confounding factors associated with genetic modifications or fluorescent labels and dyes. Moreover, the electrophysiology approach also has a lower risk of cellular damage as compared to the phototoxicity issue in long-term fluorescent imaging.

To further refine the technique, employing microfluidic systems in the recording platform provides cellular microenvironments mimicking the *in vivo* parameters needed in cell culture systems, which enable chronic measurement to be conducted with high spatiotemporal resolution. [14] It establishes the islet culture with precise fluidic control, allowing dynamic glucose stimulation and nutrient supply through medium exchange perfusion instead of merely creating a static culture environment. [9] In this way, islets' functionality would still be preserved during the evaluation, enhancing their viability both pre- and post-transplantation. Additionally, involving miniaturization and automation with the microfluidic-based device eliminates the concerns about the personnel skills and simultaneously increases the assessment throughput.

Based on the described challenges and opportunities, this project aims to develop an electrophysiology recording platform to monitor extracellular activities in intact murine pancreatic islets as the model. The platform includes integrated microfluidic perfusion systems with hydrodynamic trapping and planar gold microelectrode arrays for interfacing with the islets, also the front-end electronics on the signal acquisition system.

1.2 Problem

Islet transplantation procedures for treating diabetic patients often face challenges related to the low number of viable islets and inconsistency in their quality. Existing methods for islet functionality assessments, such as glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) quantified through enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA), are often tedious and time-consuming, making them impractical for time-sensitive pre-transplantation evaluation. It also only represents the averaged population response, making it impossible to omit the non-functioning or low-quality islets from the

population and reduce the total functioning islets yield. Moreover, the high percentage of discarded islets following infusion due to graft failure-associated issues further emphasizes the need for an assessment method that preserves the islet's function and viability during the process.

Given these limitations in the widely available islet quality assessment techniques, the thesis addresses the main question of how a platform should be developed to facilitate a rapid and user-friendly islet functionality assessment that integrates microfluidic and extracellular electrophysiological recording. Based on the raised question, the problems addressed in this thesis are outlined as follows:

1. How can an extracellular electrophysiology platform be developed to enable rapid and user-friendly assessment of islet functionality?
2. What are the requirements for integrating microfluidics with microelectrode arrays for extracellular electrophysiological recording?
3. How effective are hydrodynamic trapping in microfluidics trap and position islets for functionality assessment with microelectrode arrays?
4. What parameters need to be optimized in the microelectrode arrays to record extracellular potentials from islets effectively?
5. How can front-end electronics be designed to acquire electrical signals from islets effectively?
6. What experimental protocols and signal processing algorithms are needed to validate the platform?

1.3 Purpose

Ultimately, the main objective of the thesis is to establish a framework to develop a new platform to assess islet functionality, addressing the critical gaps in the existing techniques. Specifically, the focus is identifying the extracellular recording signals in response to glucose stimulation. Hence, the project aims to develop an integrated microfluidic and microelectrode array device that can automatically trap and place islets on the recording site and perform glucose stimulation perfusion for continuous GSIS. The device is customised to observe intact islets' physiological response at the single-islet level to provide more robust and representative results compared to

existing population-based techniques. The purpose of the thesis is described in the following points:

1. Designing and fabricating a microfluidic device for dynamic glucose stimulation perfusion and hydrodynamic trapping for single-islet entrapment.
2. Designing and fabricating microelectrode arrays tailored to pancreatic islet dimensions and compatible with microfluidic trapping.
3. Designing front-end electronics to record μV -scale extracellular potentials from islets with a digital oscilloscope.
4. Optimising fluidic control and experimental protocols for effective islet trapping, release, and medium exchange during dynamic glucose stimulation.
5. Assembling the microfluidic device and the microelectrode arrays together and interfacing them with the front-end electronics.
6. Implementing signal processing algorithms in Python for offline analysis of the recorded data.

1.4 Goal

The overall goal of this project is to investigate the feasibility of developing a platform to perform electrical recording of insulin secretion response from mice pancreatic islets following glucose stimulation. To reach the aim, the platform was divided into three primary subsystems: a microfluidic device to perform perfusion and islets localisation on top of the recording electrode, a microelectrode array to record the extracellular potential from islets, and the front-end electronics of signal acquisition setup to be connected to FPGA-based digital oscilloscope. In laying the foundation of the project, here are the goals for the initial phase:

1. Perform an interdisciplinary literature review forming the foundation of the project.
2. Create the research framework, outlining the platform's design, fabrication, and evaluation plans.

The main goal of the microfluidic subsystem is to facilitate precise islet trapping at designated locations—where the recording electrodes are placed—while minimizing

mechanical stress and preserving its functionality. In addressing the questions, the microfluidic subgoals are divided into the following objectives:

1. Design and fabricate a microfluidic platform for single-islet entrapment.
2. Optimise sample delivery and fluidic control mechanism for effective islet trapping and medium exchange perfusion in dynamic glucose stimulation.
3. Investigate trapped islets' behavior and optimal placement within the microfluidic and microelectrode interface.

In the microelectrode arrays and the front-end electronics subsystems, the main goal is to initiate a proof-of-concept platform and experimental protocols in the context of murine pancreatic islets GSIS test with extracellular recording. Thus, the subgoals for these subsystems are further divided into the following aims:

1. Develop a planar gold microelectrode array (MEA) tailored to the pancreatic islets dimension and microfluidic trapping.
2. Develop front-end electronics suitable for acquiring μV -scale biosignals.
3. Integrate the microfluidic platform with the planar microelectrode arrays for islet interfacing.
4. Integrate hardware subsystems, including microfluidics, microelectrode arrays, and front-end electronics.
5. Implement algorithms for offline digital signal processing using Python.
6. Evaluate the developed platform, identifying flaws and areas for future improvement.

Upon completion of the project, an in-depth discussion will follow to identify the needed advancements in electrode design and fabrication for optimised signal quality in islet recordings.

1.5 Research Methodology

The project adopts an interdisciplinary research approach involving literature study and experimental analysis to address the project goals. The literature study forms the project foundation and begins with an in-depth review of various

publications, including journal articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters across disciplines relevant to the main objectives. This phase aims to gain a holistic understanding of the context and investigate relevant strategies, techniques, and theoretical frameworks.

After establishing the research questions in discussion with the supervisors, the references were identified through publication databases. The extensive literature review was conducted on topics including, but not limited to, diabetes and pancreatic islets physiology, electrogenic cells and islets electrophysiology, microelectrode arrays for extracellular recordings, strategy for cells and organoid attachment on microelectrode arrays, hydrodynamic trapping in microfluidics, device fabrication techniques, front-end electronics for signal acquisition, and electrophysiological signal conditioning and interpretation. The literature study was not limited to solely the foundation of the project initiation phase, but also continually checked throughout the project as the basis during the development and experimental stage, including to guide the troubleshooting phase in the final part after the data analysis phase.

The experimental part of this project employs design, fabrication, and evaluation phases, each contributing to the development of both the individual subsystems and the integrated platform as a whole. Hardware subsystems are divided into microfluidics, microelectrode arrays, and front-end electronics, while the software subsystem centers on the signal-processing algorithms. The work begins with designing, fabricating, and evaluating the microfluidic systems, followed by designing and fabricating the planar gold microelectrode arrays (MEAs). Key schemes in the design phase include configuring the microfluidic template and the microelectrode array photomasks for cleanroom fabrication, also simulating and designing front-end electronics tailored to acquire the μV -scale biosignal.

Subsequent fabrication involves cleanroom fabrication utilising standard photolithography and lift-off techniques, followed by the non-cleanroom procedures on soft lithography. The integration phase explores various bonding and manual alignment techniques, aiming to combine the PDMS microfluidic system with the glass and SU-8 interface on the electrodes. Finally, the evaluation phase involves offline digital signal processing conducted in Python. The work distribution consists of 20% literature study, 30% fabrication, 30% measurement, and 20% data analysis. Various protocols were optimized during the experimental phase to enhance signal acquisition

across all subsystems.

1.6 Delimitations

This thesis focuses on developing a platform for studying exclusively mouse pancreatic islet behavior in extracellular recordings on GSIS tests and does not extend to human islets. The project was conducted over a total period of 30 weeks (20-week thesis work and a 10-week initial development phase from the EK2210 Project in Microsystem Technology course). The overall platform development and validation nature in the project would be exploratory, as a foundation to define the feasibility of developing the platform through a combination of several prototyping and pilot tests instead of comprehensive quantitative validation due to limitations in timeframe and resources constraining the scope and depth of the project execution.

Initially, the project aimed to explore microfluidic trapping mechanisms and potentially incorporate 3D electrodes to enhance islet-electrode contact. However, the limited time frame and resources shifted the project scope to focus solely on planar electrodes for preliminary testing with the islets. Further design iterations and cleanroom fabrication exploration on the electrodes are also restricted due to the same issue.

Most importantly, the lack of access to established electrophysiology recording systems resulted in the mandatory development of in-house hardware and software solutions, which led to extended project scope beyond the initial plan. While the team has expertise in various areas, specialised knowledge of extracellular electrophysiology recordings in islet activity was gained simultaneously along the progress, and significant time investments were thus spent in troubleshooting and in-depth literature review to grasp detailed behavior and signal characteristics.

1.7 Thesis Outline

The thesis is divided into six chapters, in the following order: Chapter 1 describes the research background and objectives. Chapter 2 provides a literature review on the state-of-the-art, presenting relevant background about existing methodologies and considerations needed to be taken to develop the desired platform. Chapter 3 presents

the methodology and the details of the platform design and implementation to achieve the purposes. Chapter 4 provides the results and analysis of the device and platform, and connects them to the existing and solved problems. Chapter 5 evaluates the findings from Chapter 4 and contextualises the parts that could be developed more and the suggestions. Chapter 6 is the final part, summarising the conclusions obtained from the project and proposing suggestions for future work.

Chapter 2

Background

The effective evaluation of pancreatic islet functionality prior to transplantation is crucial in ensuring the successful outcome of islet allotransplantation therapy for type I diabetes (T1D). The key challenges in the procedure are the inconsistent quality and low percentages of viable islets. To understand the rationale behind the intended platform, it is important to delve into the underlying physiological dynamics of pancreatic islets, assess the available strategies and methods for islet functionality evaluation, and explore the challenges faced in the field. This chapter provides a comprehensive background from various aspects, from the role of pancreatic islets in glucose homeostasis, how electrophysiology recording is interpreted, to the role of microfluidics and microelectrode arrays in the field.

2.1 Diabetes Mellitus and Type 1 Diabetes

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic disorder occurring from the inability to maintain glucose homeostasis and characterised by persistent hyperglycemia directly related to increased blood glucose levels. It stands as one of the most challenging health crises in the world today, with recent statistics reporting 537 million adults diagnosed worldwide. Notably, Europe is regarded as the region with the highest prevalence among children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes (T1D), with 295,000 in number. [15, 16] The prevalence has been increasing over time and is expected to reach 700 million adult patients globally by 2045. [17]

DM is often referred to as two primary types based on their underlying cause linked to

the disruption or dysfunction of pancreatic islets in maintaining glucose homeostasis is the main cause in DM. T1D emerges when over 80% of pancreatic beta cell loss occurs due to immune system attacks, while type 2 diabetes (T2D) results from insufficient functional beta cells due to reduced insulin sensitivity from prolonged hyperglycemia. Both types disrupt the regulatory system of glucose homeostasis, leading to severe complications and comorbidities such as vascular damage to the kidneys, eyes, nerves, and cardiac systems. [1, 17]

Nowadays, the standard treatment for T1D and T2D mainly relies on periodic insulin administration and routine blood glucose monitoring, compensating for the partial or total loss of glucose homeostatic functions. [5] This field has evolved significantly, with established protocols now incorporating the administration of human recombinant insulin through daily injections or pump devices. The therapy combines both a basal dose of long-acting insulin for maintaining a stable basal baseline and short-acting bolus doses at mealtimes. Recent advancements have further improved the treatment efficacy and practicality, such as involving closed-loop systems that integrate continuous glucose sensors and control algorithms for dose delivery management. [18]

Despite how those established treatments are working impeccably in most cases, especially with lifestyle interventions and management, the rest of the severe chronic issues leading to degenerative comorbidity from the inability to avoid hyperglycemia still remain. Maintaining near-normal glucose levels has been associated with slower progression of retinopathy, nephropathy, and diabetic neuropathy, as well as declining microvascular complications in T1D patients. [19] Furthermore, hypoglycemia poses a significant issue, with an increased risk of severe hypoglycemia requiring emergency care in patients pursuing insulin therapy. [20]

For those reasons, achieving long-term normoglycemia is an important aim in diabetes treatment. The clinical focus is shifting towards novel therapies that could restore insulin independence and address the wider spectrum of endocrine functions beyond insulin secretion in maintaining normoglycemia. It is particularly vital for T1D patients facing severe hypoglycemia, leading to whole pancreas or pancreatic islet transplantation in the most severe cases. [2, 5]

2.2 Pancreatic Islet Transplantation

Pancreatic islet transplantation has been one of the anticipated treatments for diabetes, particularly in T1D patients with severe complications. [2] The transplantation with Edmonton protocol has been established since 2000 and has become a preferred therapy for patients with a high hypoglycemia risk profile. [21] Unlike insulin injections that merely control insulin levels, islet transplantation provides a more holistic glycemic control by regulating both insulin and glucagon secretion. While the whole pancreas transplantation would offer similar benefits, the surgical procedure involved in the process is much more complicated, making islet transplantation a more viable direction.

The islet allotransplantation procedure typically involves intraportal infusion or intrahepatic engraftment of isolated pancreatic islets from a deceased donor into the patient's liver's portal vein. [3, 4] Regardless of the potential, the success rate and clinical outcomes in terms of metabolic function improvement heavily rely on the number of functioning islets and a high percentage of successful engraftment. Obstacles from the inconsistent islet quality and high rate of dismissed islets from islet graft failure arise as the main questions many researchers try to solve. [4] Other than the quality inconsistency, the post-transplantation graft failures are attributed to different variables, including the immunotoxicity or inflammatory reaction, revascularisation issues, or hypoxia-related events which might come from non-ideal transplantation site or immunosuppressive effect. [1, 22, 23]

Given the context, it is then crucial to establish proper islet quality assessment prior to transplantation to sort out non-functioning islets and ensure high throughput of functioning islets. The transplantation outcome can also be predicted by performing an islet potency test to assess their post-transplantation viability.

2.3 Role of Pancreatic Islets and Beta Cells in Glucose Homeostasis and Their Physiology

As an organ, the pancreas has a dual role in digestion and metabolism, with its main exocrine function to regulate macronutrient digestion and endocrine function of maintaining metabolic glucose homeostasis. The pancreas secretes digestive enzymes

into the duodenum via the pancreatic duct and endocrine hormones, particularly insulin, into the bloodstream. [18] While over 98% of pancreas composition consists of exocrine and acinar cells, the endocrine pancreatic islets are only taking up to 2% of the organ. [24]

Pancreatic islets are highly vascularised clusters of endocrine cells composed of five cell types (alpha, beta, delta, gamma, and epsilon cells). Among the whole intact islet composition, beta cells take 60-70% of the composition, carrying out their primary role of regulating glucose homeostasis by releasing insulin into the bloodstream. Other than producing insulin, beta cells also secrete amylin (or islet amyloid polypeptide, IAPP) and C-peptide. The other endocrine cell types in islet are the glucagon-secreting alpha cells, which represent 20–30% of the composition, followed by 3-10% of delta cells releasing somatostatin, gamma cells responsible for pancreatic polypeptide (PP) of 3-5% the cells, and epsilon cells secreting ghrelin for 1% of the islet. [17, 24]

From the morphology, pancreatic islets are characterised by their spherical geometry, with an average diameter of 150 μm and size distribution ranging from 30 to 400 μm in human islets and 20-350 μm those in mice. [24, 25] An insightful study by MacGregor et al. reports that smaller islets, those with a diameter of less than 125 μm , exhibit higher overall performance and viability compared to larger ones, which are over 150 μm in diameter. From their study on adult rat islets, smaller islets demonstrated a 20% higher viability and lower rate of necrotic and apoptotic cells. The larger islets tend to have scattered necrotic and apoptotic cells across the whole islets, particularly in the nucleic regions, while the smaller islets have only dead cells on their periphery. Furthermore, the oxygen uptake was found to be twice as high in smaller islets, representing more mitochondrial activities.

The baseline where the secretion is minimal is called basal condition. In terms of their insulin secretion profile, small islets outperformed the larger ones significantly, with three times more insulin production under basal conditions in static incubation, four times in high-glucose concentration with perfusion, and five times in response to depolarisation with potassium, compared to their larger islets counterparts. [26]

The mechanism of insulin secretion in beta cells begins when the increase in blood glucose concentration activates the glucose transporter (GLUT), where the glucose uptake and the subsequent conversion into adenosine triphosphate (ATP) results in insulin exocytosis. The glucose conversion into ATP is initiated by metabolic pathways,

including glycolysis, the Krebs cycle, and the electron transport chain, which triggers the stimulus-secretion coupling in multiple beta cells. The metabolic process would then be followed by the rest of the signalling transduction involving a procedural ionic mechanism leading to insulin granule release from beta cells. When glucose enters beta cells through GLUT, they are converted into pyruvate through a glycolytic pathway and enter the TCA cycle. Further conversion into ATP produced from pyruvate then increases the intracellular ATP/ADP ratio, which closes the ATP-sensitive potassium channel (K_{ATP}) and triggers the plasma membrane depolarisation. The membrane depolarisation would then open the voltage-dependent calcium channels, and the surge of cytosolic calcium increases the intracellular calcium concentration. As a result, the intracellular calcium flux triggers the exocytosis of insulin granules. [17]

Insulin secretion follows a biphasic time course, with a rapid and transient increase in secretion rate within the first 4-8 minutes of high-concentration glucose stimulation, followed by a further decrease but sustained phase of gradual increment in the second phase lasting throughout the glucose stimulation. The secretion profile is inherently pulsatile, oscillating in synchrony with the changes in cytoplasmic intracellular calcium levels and extracellular potentials. The calcium oscillations are key indications of the insulin secretion pulses, as well as the co-secretion of peptides and ions such as C-peptide, Zn^{2+} ions, and amylin, which are indirectly connected to insulin secretion quantification and kinetics. [17, 24]

In addition to glucose as the primary stimuli, the overall endocrine response within intact islets results from a complex network of paracrine and autocrine interactions in feedback loops. These interactions not only modulate insulin secretion but also respond to other factors stimulating or inhibiting the process. For instance, somatostatin and ghrelin inhibit beta cells' insulin secretion in the presence of glucose, while the presence of long-chain unsaturated fatty acids and glucogenic amino acids stimulate insulin production. [27, 28] The synchronized insulin secretion from multiple beta cells itself is hypothesized to derive from electrical coupling through gap junctions and paracrine signals, including nitric oxide and GABA. [29–31] Moreover, their interconnectivities are also influenced by cholinergic innervation signals and involvement of speculated pacemaker hub cells regulating beta cells network activity through diffusive paracrine signals. [3, 24] The unique systemic interaction emphasises more on the importance of preserving the complete endocrine function of whole islets rather than relying solely on insulin injection in diabetes

treatment.

The intricate endocrine responses within islets, including somatostatin, ghrelin, pancreatic polypeptide (PP), and other co-secreted ions and neurotransmitters, form a complex network all crucial for glucose homeostasis. These complex interplays demonstrate the need to consider glucose homeostasis as a synergistic network involving different cell types in the islets and their signaling pathways. For instance, the secretion of PP, along with ion and amino acids from beta cells, provides both stimulatory and inhibitory effects on glucagon secretion and contributes to their pulsatile secretion behavior. Similarly, the amylin production as a neurotransmitter adds another layer to the overall synergy of the islets' endocrine function. [3, 24]

The average normal insulin secretory oscillation usually lasts around 6-10 minutes in humans, depending on the individual glucose metabolism. In diabetic patients, the circadian rhythm of insulin secretion is afflicted due to reduced glucose tolerance and inability to maintain glucose homeostasis. [31] The oscillatory pulse amplitude, interval, and frequency related to insulin secretion are thus varying case by case, which has the prospect to correlate those variables as the indicators of the regulatory system performance representing the glucose homeostatic functions within the islets.

2.4 Overview of Pancreatic Islets Isolation and Functionality Assessment Techniques

2.4.1 Isolation of Pancreatic Islets

The isolation process and the following post-isolation functionality assessment are both crucial aspects of the pre-transplantation procedure. The primary objective during isolation and culture of pancreatic islets from the pancreas donor is to acquire the maximum number of viable islets while preserving their endocrine function. The isolation process typically consists of three primary steps: enzymatic digestion to detach the islets from surrounding exocrine tissue, mechanical digestion by aspiration or agitation to separate them from acinar tissues, and post-isolation culture.

In mice, which is the animal model used in this project, the isolation procedure begins with abdominal incision and cannulation of the common bile duct (CBD) to inject collagenase into the pancreas, ensuring a higher yield of islets. The enzyme digestion

involves the injection of collagenase into the CBD, allowing collagenase to spatially reach and dissociate the islets from their surrounding exocrine tissue effectively via vascular perfusion. Further islets dissociation from the pancreatic tissue can also be done by performing mechanical digestion of aspiration, shaking, or centrifugation, and followed by the subsequent washing and purification method. In the purification step, some protocols employ the utilization of a gradient medium or manual handpicking to select the islets from the suspension culture carefully. [32]

The last part of the isolation procedure is the culture, where the islet has to be cultured for at least 16 hours following the isolation to let it recover from the harsh digestion process. [32] Culture medium with 11 mM glucose is reported to support higher viability and less apoptosis rate statistically compared to other concentrations in rodent islets, where lower concentration down-regulates the glucose metabolic key genes and reduces the insulin content, while more concentration leads to toxicity. [33] Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 is a common culture media for islets suspension culture, normally supplemented with a mix of 10% (v/v) of Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS), 2 mM of Glutamate, and 1% of penicillin-streptomycin (100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin) to enhance their viability and minimise contaminations. The islets are cultured at a specific density to avoid nutrient competition and are kept in a sterile incubator with controlled conditions to maintain glucose sensitivity and prevent apoptosis. Glucose sensitivity is reported to be maintained at least one week in mouse pancreatic islets culture with routine medium change, but may also last only 1-4 days in a culture based on a report on culture duration and variation impact to cytoplasmic calcium oscillation from Gilon et.al. [34]

Some of the primary challenges in pre- and post-transplantation of islets following the isolation process mostly stem from apoptosis and hypoxia-induced function loss. [24] The quality of isolated islets is affected by different variables that have to be attended to, including the type and concentration of digestion enzyme used, the digestion process temperature and duration, the employed purification method, and the culture conditions. Those factors require careful consideration during the isolation and culture stage, to maintain islets functionality and enhance their transplantation viability, particularly on their ability to establish vascularisation and engraftment post-transplantation. [23]

To ensure optimal viability and functionality, it is highly crucial to assess the islets, starting from the use of the simplest techniques of visual islets morphology inspection under a microscope, monitoring cell death symptoms through evaluations with fluorescent microscopy and DNA-binding dyes, to directly measure their metabolic response in intracellular calcium measurements or GSIS test assays. [32] In basic research settings, islets' dimension, morphology, and structural integrity might provide certain clues connected to their functionality, for instance, shape abnormalities often indicating decreased viability or necrotic nucleic regions in larger islets. Digital assessment with microscopy based on the IEQ and islet purity determination are commonly utilised for this specific purpose. [7] However, in clinical settings, much more comprehensive assessments are obligatory, which brings the field into the development of various distinct assessment techniques and strategies to analyse pancreatic islets.

2.4.2 Pancreatic Islets Functionality Assessment

A variety of strategies and techniques have been established to investigate islets' functionality and their potency in transplantation, with their respective benefits and drawbacks from different working principles or aspects of study. The main objective of islet functionality assessment is to differentiate viable and functioning islets from impaired ones in order to increase the reliably isolated islets' yield and maximize the transplantation success rate. Other than confirming their viability and function, the assessment also aims to get information on their secretion profile dynamics. Another term that is commonly used in the field is the islet potency test, which refers to the assessment to predict their ability in graft function based on their viability in terms of the metabolic response or the cell morphology and nucleic membrane integrity. In other words, islet potency tests are part of the functionality assessment, which is more focused on predicting their post-transplantation properties.

Principally, the measure of isolated islets' endocrine function is mostly based on the glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) tests, which refers to the investigation of their physiology performance in producing insulin following different glucose concentrations. The gold standard of the GSIS test is defined with the involvement of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) to quantify the proportion of the secreted insulin in basal and active conditions. Although it is already established and

commonly used as the standard protocol in different islets studies, routine isolated islets evaluation through GSIS test with ELISA involves a lot of tedious processes such as aliquoting the islets, handling the liquid, and performing the ELISA, which is very time-consuming if it is performed to a vast amount of islets and involves complicated protocols which need trained personnel. [35]

With more detailed information required, islet potency assessment itself involves a more thorough investigation of insulin secretion to predict their post-transplantation viability and functionality. Employing static GSIS assessment alone does not provide sufficient information to predict graft function, primarily due to the lack of temporal resolution. While it is widely used either in measuring insulin secretion in response to glucose or drug stimuli, it does not capture the entirety of the secretion process and fully depicts the secretion dynamics essential for accurately predicting their post-transplantation functionality.

For that reason, the potency assessments are typically performed by combining different techniques accompanied with the long-established GSIS protocols or a longitudinal approach of transplanting the designated human pancreatic islets into immunodeficient (ID) nude mice to observe their *in vivo* properties. The *in vivo* potency assays are pursued to predict the clinical transplantation outcome, aimed at characterising the insulin secretory response to selectively choose which of those islets are capable of restoring normoglycemia and establishing graft function post-transplantation when being transplanted into diabetic recipients. Despite the highly representative results, the potency assessment needs a hugely long time to get results of several weeks, which often is not the time privilege the patients has and brings even more impracticality to the pre-transplantation workflow. Therefore, a rapid islet potency test with minimal operation assessing dynamic pancreatic islets' insulin secretory function becomes necessary to substantially improve the clinical workflows for islet transplantation.

Fundamentally, the assessment techniques towards pancreatic islet functionality must account for the physiological relevance of their dynamic and oscillatory nature in insulin secretion. Continuous perfusion systems are gaining attention as they result in better long-term viability and provide better accuracy in general by mimicking the physiological dynamics of glucose delivery and insulin release via the blood vessel. Another consideration is how the evaluation of a group of islets simultaneously

does not provide an accurate representation of each individual islet's physiological condition. Population-based techniques often average the bulk batch response, resulting in a generalised response that hinders the sorting of non-viable islets. Functionality tests based on each individual islet would then provide a more robust and effective analysis result, with a more representative functional assessment as opposed to the evaluation involving an averaged response of a population that does not reflect the specific response of individual islets.

In addressing the defined requirements, an integrated platform that can deliver various stimulations while simultaneously monitoring the insulin secretion process is a substantial solution in the pre-transplantation screening. The stimuli to be delivered can be in the form of glucose or other secretagogues and physiological signals possibly represented by certain drugs. The approach of using a microphysiology system not only mimics physiologically relevant aspects to predict islets functionality post-transplantation but also has more representation of assessment by simulating in vivo conditions of intact islets in the bloodstream. Employing capillary flow with microfluidics replicates the necessary microenvironment, thus providing more reliable results through dynamic stimulation and constant perfusion of nutrients and glucose. Further advancement can also be realised by mimicking the surrounding membrane and interactions of islets with vascular endothelial cells, offering a more representative monitoring of their insulin secretion process. [7]

2.4.3 Role of Microfluidics in Pancreatic Islet Functionality Assessment

Microfluidics technology offers the possibility to automate the process, thereby increasing throughput with minimal operation handling and allowing for multimodal assessment with different parameters and techniques to achieve a more dynamic and physiologically relevant analysis. The precise fluidic flow in microfluidics facilitates gentle perfusion, which improves the islets' viability in culture and maintains their functionality during the assessment. [35] Aside from the aforementioned benefit, continuous assessment are also enabled by employing a localisation or trapping mechanism to analyse individual intact islets, resulting in better accessibility in diminishing the non-functioning islets rather than the whole islet batch assessment. [7, 35] In addition, the microfluidic platform serves multiple purposes beyond cell loading

and entrapment, including long-term culture, onsite islet staining, and imaging measurement. As a result, automating the protocols minimise human error and improve assessment reliability. [24]

Microfluidic-based assessment platforms can be developed into a variety of novel islet functionality and potency tests. The primary perspectives of the assessment are further categorised based on their broad focus on utilising different principles and strategies, whether on secreted insulin profiles as analyte detection or focusing on the signals from cellular and membrane activity representing the secretion process instead. Additionally, the main interest of each assessment also differs from the taken perspective and aspect of the study, starting from the dynamics of insulin production with or without the other hormones' presence (for instance, glucagon or somatostatin), in vivo test observing diabetic reversal capability in a certain period of time, to the in vitro observation through different stimulus involving dynamic perfusion for GSIS tests or the more advance strategies of measuring intracellular calcium flux. In detail, those might refer to the evaluation of the amount of insulin secreted from high-concentration glucose stimulation as an endpoint data, the insulin secretion dynamics with more temporal information throughout the process, and other factors connected to the secretion kinetics.

Overall, pancreatic islets functionality and potency study on the insulin secretion dynamics covers a broad spectrum of aspects, with the central attention regarded to the coordinated calcium oscillations and the regulatory role of gap junctions in insulin secretion or continuous monitoring of insulin secretion under varying glucose concentration stimuli representing their response to different physiological conditions. The research direction, particularly those utilising microphysiological systems with microfluidics, is recently leading towards dismissing the downstream analysis to increase the analysis throughput and reducing the time spent.

2.4.4 State-of-the-Art in Pancreatic Islet Functionality Assessment

Dynamic GSIS tests have been preferred to provide more temporal details of the secretion process initiation from the stimuli introduction to the endpoint secretion results. In this way, when the approach is emphasising the secreted insulin as the main parameter, the local insulin accumulation could be avoided by the perfusion,

which minimises the insulin builds and increases the measurement accuracy. [7] To avoid the need for downstream ELISA for insulin quantification in dynamic GSIS, other methods have been explored on different physiological and pathophysiological characteristics such as the cytosolic calcium flux with fluorescence imaging, fatty acid oxidation, oxygen consumption rates (OCR), reactive oxygen species, ADP/ATP ratios, or the mitochondrial integrity. Additionally, some also explored the cell membrane capacitance and cytoplasmic conductivity to gain information on the stimulus-secretion coupling triggered by the high glucose concentration. [35] Indicative islets' metabolic activity, such as mitochondrial health and oxygen consumption rates and genomic analysis to identify the islets' single-cell omics on certain biomarkers such as specific miRNA, long noncoding RNA, or transcripts are also becoming popular. While the metabolic and genomic information provides rapid information on declining islet viability, they do not offer the full direct context connected to the insulin secretion function and process and have undefined relation in the different cell heterogeneity within intact islets. [2, 7] Hence, the gap consequently leaves room to focus more directly connected parameters to the secretion process itself to investigate their actual potency.

Some investigations into utilising microfluidics to investigate the relation of mitochondrial activity to insulin secretion patterns have also been conducted, with a major focus on the effects of hypoxia on the insulin secretion process and their kinetics across the population of islets to represent their viability and functionality. [4] The other approach pays attention to the glucagon secretion or the secretory dynamics of insulin and IAPP instead to gain a comprehensive view of their interplay in overall endocrine functions. This strategy of observing the coordination of insulin secretion from different cell types within islets and their influence on the insulin secretion oscillatory patterns are all intricate aspects that highlight the complex nature of islet functionality. [24] Regardless of their respective advantages, the aforementioned strategies share the same drawbacks in retrospective analysis issues similar to *in vivo* potency, which does not provide the quantification of islet survival and graft function prediction forward. Moreover, although an indication of metabolic activity with mitochondrial health and oxygen consumption rates enables rapid viability tests, they do not immediately reflect the islets' insulin secretion function, which then would not be reliable enough to be used to represent their potency.

Cellular activity in the endocrine system can be monitored by assessing their secretory

profiles representing the secreted analyte or other related biomarkers connected to the process. In insulin secretion, the resulting parameters are represented in the form of a secretory index based on static incubation, cytosolic calcium flux response in rapid glucose stimulation, hyperglycaemic mice reversibility, or the low-glucose shut-off setpoint. [36]

Various approaches have been explored to parameterise insulin secretion and other vital parameters indicating the process. One of the most pursued methods to characterise islet secretion profile is by employing online immunoassays with microfluidics and different transducers detecting secreted insulin from islets. Electrochemical measurements of amperometry and voltammetry are commonly employed to sense analytes secreted from islets by capturing oxidation and reduction reactions in the change of current. Similar to those, impedance spectroscopy or field-effect transistors (FET) offer other perspectives by detecting changes in electrical impedance across different frequencies or electrical fields, respectively, from the interaction of insulin with the biorecognition elements or nanoparticles on the transducer's surface. Insulin sensors integrating microfluidic with electrode modification involving aptamers, molecularly imprinted polymers (MIP), or nanoparticles are commonly chosen as the approach. The main challenges in those approaches are, however, the risks of electrode fouling and the involvement of biorecognition elements or nanomaterial modification to the electrodes, which adds more variables and complexity to be considered in the setup. [24, 37]

To dismiss this particular factor, an exploration into surface plasmon resonance (SPR) provides a label-free method, where integration of optical fibers and waveguide nanostructures enables their miniaturisation into a microenvironment setup. [36] The other similar techniques of online localised surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) also offer promising directions for label-free and real-time analyte measurement. [17] While this approach shows potential for direct and continuous monitoring of secreted insulin from the islets, functionality assessment based on analyte detection still faces obstacles in their dispersion and variability. Analyte detection requires high attention and meticulous control over chemical gradients to capture the spatiotemporal resolution of produced insulin accurately. [7, 35] Therefore, analyte-based insulin secretion assessment does not look like an intriguing solution to solve the addressed issue, which brings a major shift into a more holistic analysis of the secretion process led by the strategy from electrophysiology and calcium signalling responses to glucose

stimulation.

2.4.5 High Temporal Resolution Assessment of Islets Functionality

Temporal resolution plays a crucial role in explaining the complexity behind insulin secretion dynamics, which involve the comparison of different amplitude, latency, and trajectory in both individual and batches of islets. Functionality assessment with higher temporal resolutions provides more information related to the main key and subtle behaviour of islets under different stimuli.

Insulin secretion in beta cells is essentially an electrically excitable process distinguished by fluctuations in their membrane potentials following glucose stimulation. Beta cells, as glucose sensors, induce changes in electrical activity, increase cytoplasmic intracellular Ca^{2+} , and finally initiate Ca^{2+} -dependent exocytosis. [29] Various techniques have been implemented to look into the phenomenon in detail, with the majority involving either the patch-clamp electrophysiology observing membrane currents and potential oscillations in individual islet cells or the fluorescence imaging observing calcium indicator or markers interacting with the cytosolic calcium. [36]

Patch clamp allows a detailed study of cell electrophysiology by employing a suction force to create a high-resistance seal between an electrode interface in a pipette and the cell membrane. The setup facilitates stimuli induction through intracellular infusion or extracellular bath to measure the cell currents and membrane capacitance. Microfluidic platforms have been utilised to automate single-cell trapping and combine the miniaturisation of patch clamp setup to increase the throughput. The incorporation of materials with high dielectric properties to improve signal quality results in their millisecond temporal resolutions to sense single vesicle fusion events in insulin granule exocytosis. [24] Although it has a very high signal resolution, it is highly invasive and has a very low throughput due to its complicated procedures. Furthermore, when applied to an intact islet, the single-cell techniques of patch clamp face challenges in representing the whole secretion mechanism due to difficulties in extending the interface to all cells. Technically, the setup still might be connected to one of the cells in the whole islets, but since it focuses on the individual cell membrane potentials, it still does not represent the whole physiology process within the whole islet.

On the other hand, intracellular calcium imaging is commonly used to relate the GSIS response from the extracellular glucose stimulation, representing the islet viability and function information. It relies on using calcium indicators to observe the intracellular calcium flux dynamics to gain excellent spatiotemporal resolution on the whole secretion process following glucose stimulation. Green-emitting GCaMP3 is the gold standard genetically encoded calcium indicators commonly utilised for fluorescence imaging. [38] The procedure typically involves fluorescent probes or dyes such as fura-2 acetoxy-methyl-ester (fura-2AM), fluo-3, fluo-4, and fura red. [39] However, technical issues such as the need to use transgenic islets or delivering calcium dye to the whole islet or specific cell types hinder the straightforward whole intact islet analysis on single-islet resolution. [2] Moreover, the use of fluorescent dyes might possibly add more variations in the experiment, and fluorescence imaging poses the risk of cellular damage from phototoxicity in long-term high-intensity light exposure.

In intracellular calcium imaging, significant challenges arise when comparing results from different measurements, particularly due to variables like dye properties and possible variations in long-term light source intensity with the risks of phototoxicity to the islets.

In contrast to those techniques, extracellular electrophysiology emerges as the predominant solution with detailed insights into islet cell physiology, ion transfer, and insulin release in a non-invasive way while maintaining their excellent temporal resolution without further labelling with optical probes and avoiding risks of fluorescence bleaching. [40] The approach depicts the insulin secretion kinetics from intact islets through fluctuations in membrane potentials translated into the form of extracellular field potential exhibited from the glucose-dependent response. Therefore, this particular approach is chosen to be the main principle in the project to achieve the previously defined goals.

2.5 Pancreatic Islets Electrophysiology

2.5.1 Membrane Potential Fluctuations Following Glucose Stimulation

The mechanism of insulin secretion in response to higher glucose concentration can be represented as a combination of sequential electrophysiology events. As the

ATP-sensitive potassium K_{ATP} channel closes following a rise in glucose stimulation, depolarisation of the cell membrane leads to the opening of the voltage-sensitive Ca^{2+} channel. The channel opening thus increases the flux of cytosolic Ca^{2+} into the cell, indicated by increased intracellular calcium concentration and cytosolic ATP/ADP ratio. The defined process is appointed as the K_{ATP} -dependent pathway, which coexists with other different pathways at different glucose concentration stages. According to Westermark et al. work, the K_{ATP} -dependent pathway is stipulated to depart from the closing of the K_{ATP} channel in the plasma membrane through an ATP/ADP-dependent process, resulting in the bursting mode when the calcium starts entering the cell and triggers insulin granules exocytosis. Beta cells' electrical activity starts when the membrane potential is depolarised following the glucose stimulation, represented as repetitive bursting from depolarised plateaus around -30 to -40 mV, superimposed rapid action potentials spikes of 10-20 mV, and hyperpolarised phase on -65 to -60 mV. [41]

Different cell types in pancreatic islets are connected with each other as electrically coupled cells, relying on their crosstalk communication to achieve synergic multicellular cooperation. [42] Studies on signalling mechanism and intraislet communication faces a vast amount of discovery, revealing new findings on the relation of their complex interaction in the physiological model and network. A study conducted by Hogan and Percy highlighted how intracellular calcium oscillation is coordinated by the gap junctions connecting the neighboring cells and the functional connectivity between the cell networks. [30] Furthermore, Westermark et al. present a detailed GSIS modelling from electrophysiological perspectives, which highlights the interplay between electrical and metabolic activities in islets. [41] Their model explains the mechanism behind the biphasic nature of insulin secretion and focuses solely on glucose-stimulation response without taking into account the rest of stimuli, such as acetylcholine and glucagon-like peptide-1.

Single beta cells have an electrical bursting period of 2-5 seconds, while slower bursting of 2-4 minutes is often seen from intact islets. While not immediately obvious, the electrical bursts are in sync with calcium oscillation, which becomes the main focus in calcium imaging with fluorescence microscopy, and surely synchronized with the insulin secretion. The temporal resolution, however, differs as the insulin secretion oscillations typically occur for several minutes, while the calcium oscillations are similar to those periods in slow electrical bursting but not in the action potentials

burst. The other important point to highlight is the biphasic behavior of insulin secretion, where the K_{ATP} -dependent pathway regulates the first phase 1-2 minutes post-stimulation, while the second phase 25-30 minutes after is more relevant to the K_{ATP} -independent pathway. [41]

Overall, the insulin release contains the initial rapid phase and sustained longer phase, which are combined into a biphasic process. In basal low glucose condition, mild depolarisation occurs in the beginning and is directed into AP bursts, while it becomes continuously depolarised in high glucose from the reduced K_{ATP} channel activity and more intracellular ATP/ADP ratio. During the AP bursts, the beta cells have what is called pacemaker activity of slow depolarisation with decreased K_{ATP} channel activity, which is a pause to the next AP burst. Sustained depolarisation is triggered in high glucose media, releasing insulin continuously, while it is only pulsatile secretion in low concentration. Both high glucose and potassium ion concentrations depolarise the cell membrane and trigger the insulin release from the calcium influx as the stimulus-secretion coupling. Glucose stimulation triggers a sustained release, while the potassium ions only trigger the transient and rapid release. [29]

2.5.2 Comparison of Different Electrophysiology Dynamics

The ionic transport between cell membranes generates an ionic current, which translates into action potential (AP), similar to those in neuron and muscle cells. In pancreatic islets, beta cells' endocrine response to high glucose levels is specified by the interplay between electrical and calcium signalling interaction. Beta cells from mouse islets are hyperpolarised at a resting potential of roughly -80 mV in the absence of glucose, with no electrical activity evoked. By increasing the glucose concentration to 5 mM, they slightly depolarise to a higher potential of -60 mV. Once the glucose stimulation exceeds 6 mM, they would further depolarise, and the electrical activity threshold of around -50 mV would be achieved, triggering short AP bursts with a depolarising baseline trend. Silent electrical intervals would present occasionally interrupting the AP bursts from repolarising feedback. At glucose concentrations beyond 10 mM, further extreme response would be generated with prolonged oscillatory waves and shorter silent repolarisation intervals. Meanwhile, when the glucose would pass more than 20 mM, the burst firing would then become continuous without repolarisation intervals. [29]

Similarly, human islets exhibit resting membrane potentials of around -70 mV, which depolarised into -60 mV when glucose metabolism produces ATP. As a result, the depolarised membrane prompts the opening of voltage-gated calcium Ca_v channels at a peak influx of around -30 mV. The increasing influx of intracellular calcium then triggers insulin vesicle fusion with the cell membrane, leading to insulin exocytosis. [17, 24]

While being utilised a lot to study the physiological and pharmacological molecular mechanism behind their endocrinal function, mice pancreatic islets are quite different in size and structure perspectives to humans, which have larger dimensions and more systemic connectivity. They also have different insulin granule compositions, which results in different secretion dynamics and ion channel behavior as well. Insulin secretion highly depends on the ATP from the glucose metabolism process, but certain enzymes and transporters also have big roles in the pathway. Human beta cells present similar responses in depolarisation due to the closure of K_{ATP} channels, with differences in the membrane potential and oscillation patterns than those in mice beta cells. Overall, differences in different species might be related to their distinct isolation method. For example, paracrine signaling regulates insulin secretion and is inhibited by GABA neurotransmitters, but this phenomenon does not happen in isolated beta cells. [29]

As the cells are electrically connected by gap junctions, the calcium oscillations are synchronized. Beta cells' electrical activity can be modulated by introducing either stimulating or inhibiting nutrients, hormones, peptides, amino acids, acetylcholine neurotransmitters, or drugs to manipulate the ion channel or receptors in the biochemical pathways. Modulation of the ion channels and regulating their membrane potentials in glucose metabolism by pharmacological agents are one of the most established therapies in T2D in the field recently. Certain drugs, for example, sulfonylureas, are aimed at pharmacologically manipulating K_{ATP} channel to close the channel and stimulate insulin secretion. When the action potential thresholds are achieved with, for instance, tetrodotoxin TTX-sensitive Na^+ channel in mice, beta cells generating voltage-dependent currents exist in mice but not in humans as the Na^+ channels in their beta cells are less sensitive to TTX as an inhibitor. The voltage-dependent inactivation of the Na^+ channel derived from membrane potential has more depolarised potential in beta cells compared to mice. Those mechanisms are the result of complex interplays between the intercellular communication from different cell

types within the islets and their electrical coupling. [29]

If the dynamics in the membrane potential and K_{ATP} channel activity in healthy cells and diabetic ones are compared, obvious differences highlight the source of the issue behind the conditions. Both the oscillatory insulin secretion and electrical activity are affected in healthy and diabetic beta cells, with lower action potential amplitude unable to close the K_{ATP} channel and thus dismiss the signalling pathway forward. In healthy beta cells, the K_{ATP} channel remains high at basal conditions, keeping the hyperpolarised membrane and inhibiting insulin secretion. However, in diabetic beta cells, the K_{ATP} channel in the same condition has a lower amplitude, which leads to slight depolarisation and mistakenly fired AP occasionally, resulting in elevated basal insulin secretion in T2D patients. The lower K_{ATP} activity thus causes the same high glucose concentration, affecting the diabetic cells less than healthy ones, as the depolarisation is limited and marginal AP firing and insulin release. As a result, the insulin secretion has no biphasic characteristic. Administration of sulfonylureas as a calcium channel inhibitor further reduces K_{ATP} channel activity, resulting in strong membrane depolarisation and stimulating AP firing, as well as the time-dependent AP decrease, resulting in biphasic stimulation of insulin secretion. [29]

2.5.3 Interpretation of Extracellular Potential Electrophysiology

In general, there are two types of electrical signals exhibited by the islets, which are the short-term high-frequency action potentials (AP) and long-term low-frequency slow potentials (SP). The AP bursts are correlated with cell depolarisation, while the low-frequency SP waves result from multiple cell activities interacting with each other through intraislet cell coupling. SP signals are initially silent at the basal 3 mM glucose in murine islets and would have increased frequency along with higher glucose concentrations above the secretion threshold of 15 mM. [13]

Electrical coupling between multiple beta cells presents a pivotal aspect to their electrophysiology dynamics in propagating the excitation signals and organising their stimulus-secretion coupling (SSC). [43, 44] Even though the detailed information on how those interactions and synchronicity are specifically controlled, their dynamics present an interesting basis for analysing pancreatic islets functionality. Synchronised signals from their propagation were reported to reach spikes ranging from 200-1000

ms in duration, with a firing rate of around 1-2 Hz. Meanwhile, the individual response from single beta cells typically lasts 10-50 ms in duration. [10]

The basal conditions are defined differently in the oscillatory pulse amplitude, interval, and frequency patterns between individuals based on their metabolism superimposed on the basal secretion rate. The secretion process itself has an oscillatory pattern with pulses around the basal baseline, characterised by the amplitude and time interval between the spikes. Even though important, the intervals have not been precisely measured due to the sampling frequency and assay precision in conventional methods. Therefore, it is highly important to pay attention to the noise and signal variability, employing an algorithm to identify and quantify the oscillation accurately. [3]

In intracellular calcium imaging, significant challenges arise when comparing results from different measurements, particularly due to variables like dye properties and possible variations in long-term light source intensity with the risks of phototoxicity to the islets. These factors can skew data interpretation, making it difficult to standardise results across different experiments. In the standard GSIS measurement, the optimum glucose stimulation index (SI), representing the stimulation to basal condition response, the healthy islets typically have 2-20 SI considering the sacrificed animal strain, age, and body weight. [32] As a comparison, standardised value of stimulation index in GSIS assays provide reliable comparisons with a consistent framework for interpretation, rather than relying on raw numerical data. For instance, when the islets have significant dimension differences, the islet cross-sectional area could be utilised to normalised the acquired GSIS results. [45]

Generally, the islet presents a biphasic response with a rapid spike at the insulin release, followed by declining intensity in the plateau phase, which would be the baseline during the stimulation. Compared to straightforward static stimulation, dynamic perfusion provides additional temporal information to investigate the kinetics during the insulin secretion process. [32] Based on how the signal frequency and period would change over which concentration of glucose stimulation delivered into the islets, the statistical relationship between them in extracellular potential recordings could be assessed with the fraction of the plateau phase (FOPP) parameter, which states the time fraction during which spikes are recorded.

Insulin secretion in response to extracellular glucose stimulation represents the islet function, indicating the viable and functioning islets. Even though the other hormones,

such as glucagon and somatostatin, as well as the other peptides, are also secreted from islets, insulin is a major part of the secretion, which is easier to detect. Prior to the GSIS test, the subjected islets first have to be cultured in a low glucose condition around 3 mM to put them in basal, non-stimulated condition for one hour. By introducing 11 mM glucose during the test, the stimulation process should trigger insulin secretion, where the fluctuations in their dynamic become the indicator of functioning islets. [32]

2.5.4 Signal Behaviour in Extracellular Islet Electrophysiology Recording

At the cellular level, ATP production results in the opening and closure of specific ion channels, which later on trigger the corresponding ion fluxes and consequently generate electrical current. SP from integrated synchrony between multiple beta cell activity reflects their intraislet coupling. A study reported that SP was absent at low glucose and had increased frequency at 15 mM glucose concentration. [37]

Crosstalk communication from beta cells to the other cell types within islets also presents dynamic electrophysiology behavior. Beta cells and alpha cells work in opposite electrical signalling, with beta cells bringing glucose down by secreting insulin and alpha cells liberating glucose from the liver instead by secreting glucagon. It is assumed that recording cumulative responses from different cell types, instead of merely beta cells, would increase the measurement precision. Besides, natural glycemic regulation is achieved by cross-communication between different cell types and another signalling from different tissues and organs. [46] The short-lived AP lasting only tens of milliseconds is reported to indicate single beta cell activity, while the SP wave components in the signal represent cell-to-cell interactions within intact islets. [47]

Detailed insights into beta cells' behavior under different ionic conditions have been established based on a previous study involving intracellular microelectrode. According to their work, a rise in extracellular K_o concentration to 47 mM did not induce electrical activity, although the cells were depolarised. Particularly, 60 minutes following the removal of this K_o concentration would later on generate the AP instead, indicating a reversible effect on K_o to beta cell excitability. On the other hand, the reduction of extracellular chloride Cl_o level to 12 mM did not affect the generation of AP, while a lower extracellular sodium Na_o concentration of 26 mM increased AP

spike amplitude and exhibited a more pronounced role of sodium to AP generation. When a further investigation into calcium was performed, the intermittent AP firing behavior changed into continuous firing without a silent period when dismissing the extracellular Ca_o concentration, and increasing their concentration to 25.6 mM would completely block the AP instead. Overall, the glucose-induced AP amplitude might be increased up to 20 mV by exposing extracellular concentration of Na_o at around 26 mM and Ca_o at 7.7 mM in 11.1 mM presence of glucose. [48]

Extracellular recording capability in observing intercellular coupling has been demonstrated by a prior study analyzing SP behavior generated by islets. Differential bandpass filters on separated bandwidth displayed two types of extracellular waveforms in voltage, which are AP lasting for 40-60 ms and the syncytial signal of SP lasting for 800-1500 ms. Larger SP amplitude (50-350 μ V) than AP (10-50 μ V) originates from the propagation of current flow between coupled beta cells, highlighting their physiological relevance as an indicator of stimulus-secretion coupling activation within the islet, particularly beta cells. The biphasic electrical activity started from each islet's cell activity, producing AP and pronounced coupling between cells through SP once the propagation occurs. Their signal behavior is similar to that of neurons, where the SP behaves similarly to the low-frequency local field potential (LFP) around multiple neurons. [12]

The same study also revealed a correlation between SP frequency and extracellular glucose concentration, with their frequency peaked at 10 mM level. Based on their results, SP signals were only exhibited when the ATP-dependent potassium K_{ATP} channels closed, as they were induced either by 15 mM glucose and 0.1 μ M glibenclamide but not 24 mM KCl. Furthermore, nifedipine/sulfonylurea stimulation behaves as a calcium channel blocker, reducing the glucose-stimulated SP signals. Yet, such behavior was not elicited by the KCl-induced depolarisation with unevoked SP, unlike those in calcium imaging. It was explained that calcium imaging does not require signal propagation between multiple cells to observe the event, while SP is correlated to their interconnectivity. [12]

Furthermore, the aforementioned study also pointed out that SP signals from islets representing beta cell coupling via connexin-36, which acts as an indicator of islets' syncytial glycemic control function. The conclusion was taken that introducing adrenaline to the islets resulted in unaffected AP signals but dismissed SP waveforms.

Moreover, both AP and SP existed when the glucose concentration of 15 mM was delivered, but only AP exhibited in basal 3 mM glucose. Their signal pattern indicated that SP would only exhibit once glucose stimuli or other secretagogues trigger beta cell coupling, and the AP from low glucose was exhibited mostly by alpha cells instead. [12]

Another study by Jaffredo et al. observed a biphasic profile of SP when increasing the glucose concentration to 8.2 mM after applying a 2 Hz digital filter to acquire the in-traitlet synchrony information with the -15 μ V threshold. Compared to the unicellular AP response, the multicellular SP signals require beta-cell coupling via connexin-36 to be observed. The biphasic SP profile presented a smaller amplitude with a high frequency during the first phase and an increasing amplitude with a lower frequency in the second phase. The increasing amplitude indicates the degree of beta cell synchrony, which further validates SP signal behaviour reliability to indicate islet functionality. [49]

Similar results were acquired by another study, with a further focus on signal processing to obtain high-quality recording on both the slow and rapid oscillating SP and AP from islets. The SP was observed with 100-150 μ V amplitude, and AP at 10-30 μ V, with elevated AP burst frequency from 5.5 mM, 8.2 mM, 11 mM, and 15 mM glucose concentration. Meanwhile, the SP was only discretely observed above 8.5 mM of glucose. Inversely, the reduced glucose level also lowers both AP and SP frequency. [50]

2.5.5 State-of-the-Art in Extracellular Islets Electrophysiology Platforms

Extracellular recordings provide excellent temporal resolutions, considering that the signals from islets are generated in milli or even microseconds. [12, 13, 47, 51] MEA use in analysing pancreatic islets activity, particularly beta cells, has become increasingly popular and proven to correlate with the already established strategy in analysing pancreatic islets functionality. For instance, Alassaf et al. highlight the use of MEA for islet functional assessment, demonstrating the correlation with static GSIS assays. [52]

MEA interfaces are ordinarily connected with an electrophysiology platform to perform detailed differential measurements and analysis of their electrical activities

corresponding to high glucose concentration and other stimuli. Most previous research works utilised commercial platforms coming from big companies such as National Instruments, Multi Channel Systems (MCS), or INTAN and adjusted the system and algorithm configurations to record electrophysiology signals accordingly based on the type of excitable cells and recording paradigm. Another high-end commercial system, Axion Maestro Edge, embeds its recording platform along with an incubator-like enclosure. Unfortunately, the major concern on those platforms lies in their affordability, with high-end systems such as those established by MCS costing around 50,000 USD. In an effort to address the cost barrier and democratise the electrophysiology platform, many researchers collaborate to establish open-source platforms employing INTAN RHD recording systems, such as Intsy, Willow, Piphys, NeuroRighter, and Open Ephys. The other open-source effort also resulted in several data processing and analysis software, including MEABench, ArtE, Spike, and RTXI, which enable real-time processing and configurable modular tools. [53–55] Table 2.5.1 presents a brief overview of several platforms available for extracellular electrophysiology recording.

Table 2.5.1: Specifications of Custom and Commercial MEA Platforms

Platform	Specifications	Reference
MEA1060-Inv	1100× voltage gain, 0.1-3000 Hz bandwidth, 10 kHz sampling rate, and 12-bits resolution	[12, 37, 49, 50, 54]
Custom-made (with Agilent HCPL-7800 Isolation Amplifier)	1000× voltage gain and 3.3 kHz bandwidth	[56]
INTAN RHD2000 EVAL, RHD2132	1-10 kHz bandwidth and 20 kHz sampling rate	[57]
MEA60-Inv	1200× voltage gain, 0.1-3000 Hz bandwidth, and 10 kHz sampling rate	[58]
ASIC in XFAB XH018 CMOS	1 kHz sampling rate	[59]
MEA1060-Inv	Spike detection with Xilinx Spartan 3E XC2S500E, VHDL, and Xilinx ISE design tool	[51]
Backyard Brains	900× voltage gain and 300-1300 Hz bandwidth	[60]

On the other hand, software-based solutions have processing latency issues, where the limitations on throughput originate from high data streams. FPGA-based signal processing thus becomes commonly pursued in the field to execute signal processing and spike detection to reduce the digital signal processing load. The development typically starts by integrating processing units from custom libraries embedded in FPGA with reduced processing latency and real-time feedback loop control over multiple electrode channels. [54] Another work by Oleary et al. attempted to improve the platform on the hardware system instead by establishing the open-source platform, OpenMEA, with multilevel PCB embedding sensitive electronics in a shielded head stage and applying low-voltage differential signalling for digital transmission. [61]

2.6 Hydrodynamic Trapping in Microfluidics

Hydrodynamic trapping in microfluidics provides precise immobilisation of islets toward the recording electrode, particularly manipulating the movement while infusing the culture medium or stimulation. Different arrangements of trapping array mechanisms have been established with varying shapes, such as U-shape, polygon, or butterfly geometry. Based on the 3D layout, the trapping mechanism might be realised vertically with some sort of microwell or horizontally with microposts. With further modification, microposts might be embedded on the main channel sidewall, resulting in a crossflow microfiltration system with certain flow resistance differences to ensure successful trapping. [62]

Tan and Takeuchi were pioneering the principle of microfiltration trapping using a U-cup junction embedded along a straight main channel, with further selective release ability through localised heating with a focused infrared laser resulting in bubble formation. In principle, the specified trapping channel has lower flow resistance, with a critical parameter on the channel height, which should fit the targetted particles or cells diameter but not be too large to avoid excessive fluidic flow, which attracts more than the individual target being caught simultaneously. However, the study presented suboptimal performance when polydisperse particles are involved. [63] Another study by Sauzade et al. followed up their work by designing a focusing displacement structure on the main channel before encountering the trapping site. The mechanism was based on difficulty in multiple trapped particles leading towards a clogged channel, which

utilised a filtering structure to guide the streamlines. With such a focus displacement system, their device also reduced the possibility of the trapped cells being pushed out from the trap. [64]

A detailed conceptual model for the trapping mechanism highlights the crucial feature of the trapping channel is to achieve lower flow resistance on the trapping site than the main channel, represented by R_h . Once the U-cup aperture is covered by the successfully trapped cells, they would act as a fluidic plug, which then increases the R_h and forces subsequent cells to flow through the main channel instead [65] Four critical geometry parameters of the trapping site include the minimum width W_{min} , aperture gap width W_{gap} , depth of the trapping site D_{trap} , and the depth of the aperture on the end of U-cup site D_{gap} to produce $Q_{trapsite}/Q_{mainchannel}$ ratio more than 1. [66]

Another study by Zhou et al. attempted a similar system to immobilize single cells. They modeled the fluidic hydrodynamic resistance as $R_c = \frac{\Delta P}{Q}$, where the ΔP represents the pressure drop along the channel, and Q is the volumetric flow rate. The length and geometry difference between the main channel and trapping site drives a greater flow rate in the trapping site, directing the cells into the trap site. [67] The other study on single-cell trapping highlighted critical velocity around the trapping sites. From their study, a certain threshold velocity was speculated as needed to achieve proper and efficient trapping. When the introduced flow rate within the channel is below the threshold, cells or particles cannot be trapped sufficiently. On the opposite, once the threshold is exceeded, successful trapping would occur. [68]

In the context of analyzing pancreatic islets, Silva et.al demonstrated healthy Ca^{2+} signalling supported by the reduced shear stress from the trapping system. [69] The analyzed islets typically produced dampened Ca^{2+} response following glucose stimulation at the peripheral islets, indicating shear-induced damage, hydrodynamic trapping microfluidic significantly reduced the flow velocity at the peripheral while still able to induce the intercellular stimulation through the fluidic perfusion. As an effect, the dampened response was reduced, and the system also avoided endothelial cell necrosis at the same time from the perfusion, which supports the islets' revascularisation post-transplantation. The trapping site was designed with a channel cross-sectional area to increase the fluidic resistance when the targeted islets are trapped. The microfluidic was fabricated with 125 μm height, where the trapping site was set into 300 μm wide rounded to 50 μm opening to induce lower fluidic

resistance than the bypass or main channel, $R_{\text{trapsite}} < R_{\text{mainchannel}}$, which triggered the trapping event. The resistance of the bypass channel can be adjusted by modifying the length; therefore, the length was empirically tested at 5 mm and 10 mm to observe the islets loading by gravity-driven flow. [69]

To further investigate the impact on flow resistance difference in such a system, a study focused on 2D computational fluid dynamic simulations in COMSOL Multiphysics, specifically assessing stationary laminar flow. The simulations of the study revealed that the trapping site presented a higher flow velocity Q_{trapsite} than the main channel $Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$, which at the same time exhibited lower flow resistance in the trapping site. This further clarifies the dynamics of introducing a U-cup on the main channel where the junction has lower flow resistance, which attracts the islets to go there instead. The study also pursued glucose stimulation on islets and observed the intracellular calcium response, with a rising flow rate not necessarily correlated to their calcium response, which indicated that the shear flow is limited but still able to introduce the needed stimulation and nutrition provided. [14]

To optimise islet trapping efficiency, Nourmohammadzadeh et al. demonstrated the derivation of the formula on the flow resistance between the U-cup and loop channel from Dary-Weisbach equation modified with Poiseuille's law for rectangular channels. With the aim to minimise shear force while still perceiving high trapping efficiency, the study revealed flow rate below 50 $\mu\text{l}/\text{minute}$ would prevent efficient mixing and reduce the trapping efficiency. However, too high of a flow rate, exceeding 2 mL/minute would dislodge the already trapped islets instead as they pushed through the narrow aperture gaps at the end of U-cup trap openings. [9]

Based on the formula defined in their study, high trapping efficacy could be achieved with optimised geometry on the channel length, width, and depth by paying attention to the produced $Q_{\text{trapsite}}/Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$. When the crossflow intersection close to the trapping sites has lower flow resistance, the islets would be shifted from the mainstream flow in the main channel into the trapping region. They reported with $Q_{\text{trapsite}}/Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$ of 5.5, all traps are occupied from the high flow resistance ratio. However, multiple beads were trapped. As a trade-off, with $Q_{\text{trapsite}}/Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$ of 0.7 would be insufficient, resulting in a minimal percentage of occupied traps. The channel was then optimised to achieve $Q_{\text{trapsite}}/Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$ ratio of 2.8, where 95% traps efficiency was yielded. The trapping efficacy was also reported to be independent of the

introduced concentration, with merely the loading trapped time affected. For instance, in a concentration of 500 islets/mL, the islets were trapped for less than a minute at a 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate. [9]

In order to evaluate the needed perfusion flow rate to mimic the islet microenvironment, a study evaluated different fluidic delivery with 8 $\mu\text{L}/\text{hour}$ and 25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{hour}$, which is notably slower than the other microfluidic study in 120 to 1500 $\mu\text{L}/\text{hour}$ range. Such a low flow rate is not applicable to be realised with a syringe pump, as the system tends to present significant flow oscillation once reaching those flow rate ranges. The study also reported shear values on the islets of less than 188 μPa , which is much lower than the 6 mPa shear values from the hydrodynamic trapping system. [70]

2.7 Microfluidic Fabrication

PDMS is highly preferred in microfluidic to replicate microphysiological systems for their optical transparency, biocompatibility, oxygen permeability, and straightforward patterning. [71] There are various surface treatment and bonding strategies available to integrate PDMS and different substrates, including thermal bonding, oxygen plasma surface activation, or adhesive-based and chemical gluing. Aside from plasma treatment, irreversible chemical bonds between activated or functionalised PDMS to substrate can be achieved through chemical surface functionalisation or chemical gluing by applying molecular monolayers and surface functional groups to form chemical bonds resulting in strong attachment. [71, 72]

The benefit of using silicon-based substrates, including glass, is how PDMS bonding with simplified surface activation is sufficient, as the bondable functional groups already exist. Surface activation through plasma treatment works by removing contaminants and generating reactive chemical groups for covalent bonding. It converts the hydrophobic state of PDMS to become more hydrophilic, which increases the bonding quality. Plasma treatment works by forming plasma using different ionised gasses in vacuum conditions. Oxygen plasma is highlighted to facilitate better bonding quality compared to air plasma, with additional features to perform surface cleaning. Silanol groups (-Si-OH) from silicon-based substrate and terminal methyl groups (-CH₃) in PDMS formed covalent siloxane bonds (Si-O-Si) when both surfaces interfaced together. Following the loss of water molecules in the plasma treatment,

surface oxidation on PDMS and increased hydroxyl group concentration significantly enhance their bond formation. Their crosslinking properties would differ depending on experimental conditions, such as plasma power and exposure time. To ensure hydrophilicity is generated following plasma treatment, a water drop test with contact-angle measurement is a simple way to verify sufficient surface functionalisation. [71, 72]

However, PDMS presents instability on the oxidised surface once reactive silanol groups got exposed to open air. [73] Treated PDMS regain their hydrophobicity when being exposed to normal ambient environments in a short time, between one to several minutes, with further mechanical deformation also contributing to speed up the process. Additionally, over-treated PDMS also regain their hydrophobicity state sooner. This results in difficulty in achieving precise alignment within such a short time window. [71, 72]

Additionally, molecular monolayers might be deposited on the plasma-treated surface when the glass substrate has other deposited material to enhance the bonding property. Organosilanes, for instance, 3-(aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES), form covalent bonds with the PDMS through their amino group ($-NH_2$), with important parameters affecting the bonding quality on applied concentration, temperature, and the application strategy to stabilise the self-assembled layer including rinsing, drying, and heat treatment. On the other side, when interfacing gold materials with PDMS, the bonding quality relies on how much of the terminal thiol group bonds covalently to the gold. [71] To further increase their bonding strength, a microscopic amount of adhesive as surface functionalisation is also an option. However, risks on the adhesives entering the channel make this approach commonly not preferred. [71, 72]

PDMS microfluidic bonding quality is typically observed by performing tests such as pulling, shear, peel, or leakage tests. High-quality bonding is represented by how strong the bonded surface resists high pressure or flow rates within the channel. Simple strength testing by manual peeling to forcibly remove the substrate by hand or scalpel typically should be enough, with either structural tears or clean detachment representing their discrete cohesive properties. Leakage tests also provide immediate information on the microfluidics' practicality sustaining dynamic perfusion by applying increased flow gradually to find their integrity failure point. To acquire a more quantitative result, some studies employ tensile strength, shear strength, or

burst test measurement employing relevant sensors following the bonding process. [71]

2.8 Microelectrode Arrays for Extracellular Electrophysiology

Electrochemical impedance is deemed as one of the most important properties of the recording electrode, with SNR inversely connected to their impedance. Gold was previously preferred to be selected as electrode material for its high electrical conductivity, chemical stability, and biocompatibility. [74] Nevertheless, most recent generation MEA electrodes now rarely involve a noble metal layer as the surface material interfacing the cells.

Other than their material properties, electrode dimension and geometry also have a major impact on the overall signal resolution, for instance, smaller electrodes would generally increase the spatial resolution, creating more spatially specific results. When the electrode area dimensionally matches and sufficiently covers the cells (not too small or too large), the spatial accuracy would be specific to that interfacing cell, and the results would become more selective. [75–77] However, low surface area equals higher impedance which further reduces the SNR. Conversely, a larger electrode size would present lower impedance, enhancing the signal quality, but becomes spatially less selective. Therefore, a balance between maintaining spatial detail while acquiring high-quality signals is the challenge in developing the electrode interface.

A technique to maintain both trade-offs is by modifying the electrode surface with large surface area materials, which now becomes more preferred to reduce the electrode impedance and consequently increase the SNR with lower signal attenuation while maintaining the spatial resolution. Some examples of the electrode materials and the dimension for electrophysiology experiment are illustrated in Table 2.8.1.

Electrode surface modification might employ highly conducting materials with high corrosion resistance, such as Pt black (PtB), TiN, ITO, or IrOx, and nanomaterials such as gold nanostructure/nanoflakes/nanopillars, CNT, and Ti₃N₄ as electrode coatings. Pt black and TiN have large surface areas, while ITO is preferred for transparency, and TiN and IrOx specifically present better specific charge transfer capability, which is great for stimulation purposes. [76, 84] Pt black is commonly combined to modify

Table 2.8.1: Electrode Material and Electrode Dimensions for Electrogenic Cell Studies

Electrode Material	Diameter or Area	Interelectrode Distance	Ref.
Ti/Pt	30 μm	50 μm	[37]
TiN and PEDOT-PSS on Au	10 μm and 30 μm	40 μm and 200 μm	[49]
TiN	10 \times 10 μm	100 μm	[47]
Carbon-fibre coated with PEDOT:PSS	8.4 μm	-	[38]
ITO	40 \times 40 μm	-	[56]
PtB-modified Pt	8 μm	20 μm	[78]
ITO and Pt	30 μm and 50 μm or 4 \times 4 μm and 8 \times 8 μm	150 μm and 200 μm	[79]
Stainless steel and parylene-coated tungsten	10 μm and 120 μm	-	[80]
TiN	30 μm	200 μm	[81]
TiN-coated Au pillars	20 μm and 50 μm	-	[77]
Cr/Cu	5 μm	200 μm	[82]
TiN	30 μm	-	[50]
TiN	30 μm	200 μm	[83]
TiN and PtB	30 μm	150 μm and 200 μm	[58]
Pt	30 μm and 40 μm	200 μm	[54]

platinum electrodes to improve their long-term stability while reducing the impedance. [85] Another approach is to increase the active electrochemical surface by coating TiN or IrOx. Electrode with larger surface area would exhibit lower noise, which is why electrode modification with sputtered IrOx films (SIROFs), TiN, nanostructure Pt, or conducting polymers such as PEDOT:PSS which increase the effective surface area and decrease impedance and noise. In PEDOT:PSS, higher electrochemical conductivity and charge injection capacity are observed as compared to conventional gold or platinum. When underlying substrates such as TiN and Pt are coated by rough gold electrodes, modification with TiN would significantly decrease electrode impedance and thermal noise. [77] Furthermore, platinum electrode modification with CNT is also reported to have reduced intrinsic impedance up to three orders of magnitude lower. [86] Some reports on electrode impedance involved in extracellular electrophysiology studies are shown in Table 2.8.2.

Table 2.8.2: References on Electrode Impedance for Electrogenic Cell Studies

Electrode Material	Impedance Specification	Reference
Carbon fibre and PEDOT:PSS modification	6.8 M Ω to 120 k Ω at 1 kHz	[38]
Au	22 M Ω to 11 k Ω at 20 Hz	[75]
Au	50 k Ω at 1 kHz	[76]
TiN-coated Au	7 k Ω at 1 kHz	[77]
Cr/Cu	0.43 \pm 0.024 M Ω at 1 kHz	[82]
Au	1.2 M Ω at 100 Hz, 160k Ω at 1 kHz, and 39 k Ω at 75 kHz	[57]
Pt	800-1100 k Ω	[87]
TiN	20-30 k Ω at 1 kHz	[58]

PEDOT:PSS has been employed in many organic bioelectronics systems due to their biochemical stability in an aqueous environment and ability to form both electronic and ionic interfaces, improving the interaction with living cells in electrolytes. Gold electrodes with PEDOT:PSS are reported to have much lower impedance and increased charge-injection capacity (CIC), which reduce their parasitic capacitance. [38] The other work by Abarkan et al. employed vertical OECT to perform extracellular electrical recording on mice islets and integrated electronic boards with individually tunable transistor biases. The electrodes were based on a gold surface on the source and drain,

coated with PEDOT:PSS to produce high transconductance. By employing OECT in their platform, high signal fidelity was achieved as the signals were immediately amplified at the source by the intrinsic voltage and converted into current, with high differences in minimised noise compared to metal-based electrodes. [40]

Regarding beta cells' AP, the recording highly depended on islet adhesion to the electrode and the percentage of ion channels in contact with the electrode interface. [12] Another study from Koutouras et al. also employs PEDOT:PSS to coat planar TiN electrode, with conducted surface modification to reduce the amount of noise and frequency-dependent change in impedance. The study succeeded in improving AP signal quality while still preserving the SP signal quality. In terms of geometry, 3D electrodes mimicking mushroom shapes with cell membranes conforming to the shape have been pursued, but they did not necessarily enhance AP detection. As a result, the acquisition of the AP signal improved a lot, but not much on the SP, although it was not a considerable issue since SP already has considerably robust amplitude. However, the tricky part of detecting SP lies in their low-frequency bandwidth, which acts as the trade-off when frequency-based filtering to improve AP recording would be pursued instead. [13]

Potentiometric electrochemical systems passively acquired the open-circuit potential differences from recording and grounded reference electrodes to record the electrophysiology signals in different excitable cells. Contradictory to intracellular or patch clamp recording, which penetrates the cell membrane, MEA-based extracellular presents higher signal distortion and attenuation due to more spatial distance to the cell interface. A high percentage of the overlapping physical contact between the electrode and the cell would increase signal quality. With the same principle, further distance between their interface would result in attenuated and warped signals.

Since the proper contact and cell adhesion to the electrode are the major contributors to the signal quality, the experiment protocols typically employ several strategies, including increasing cell attachment and better cell placement control to achieve maximum cell proximity to the electrode. However, surface modification with adhesive protein has less effectivity over placing the cells precisely on the recording site. [87] As an illustration, one study observed cardiomyocytes cultured on the commercial multielectrode array system for at least 6 days, where the electrodes were coated with 2 μ L of fibronectin and the effect on density on FP compared. [88] Some of

the commonly used coating materials for surface functionalisation promoting cell adhesion or tissue adherence on MEA are collagen, poly-D-lysine, poly-L-lysine, fibronectin, gelatine, or laminin. [57, 76, 82, 84, 86]

The electrical behavior of the interfacing system in the electrolytes can be analysed through impedance analysis. With insulating substrate beneath, the electrode material and substrate supposedly have no capacitance, meanwhile some of adjacent electrodes might have interelectrode capacitance and electrode-electrolyte interface also exhibit some parasitic capacitance. [86] To observe insulation layer degradation, electrochemical impedance can be monitored to ensure a perfectly insulated electrode. Electrode-electrolyte interface would have increased capacitance from medium penetration through the insulation layer when early delamination exposed the electrode and increased their effective surface area. [89]

With signals from adjacent cells recorded simultaneously, the high number of AP attenuate and temporarily filter true signals. The electrode and electrolyte interface can be modelled as resistance in parallel with capacitance, while the cell membrane is simulated as the parallel between resistance and capacitance. Meanwhile, the electrolyte between the electrodes and the cell interface generates conduction resistance (R_{seal}), which varies electrolyte characteristics and affects the electrical current flow later on. The R_{seal} has a critical role in the signal attenuation, with R_{seal} in $M\Omega$ range translating into μV scale signals. The interface between the metal electrode and electrolyte is characterised by a capacitive process. [84] When multiple electrodes interface electrolyte, DC offset would be generated from their half-cell potential with non-ideal similarity, which got amplified along the analog circuitry and saturating the signals. This DC offset can be reduced by employing active HPF to attenuate the low-frequency noisy components.

2.9 Front-end Electronics

A recent review published by Chen et al. presents a comprehensive overview of important design considerations in developing a neural recording platform. Although it might not seem like a straightforward comparison, neural signals present signal frequency bandwidth equivalent to those in extracellular islet recording. Their work highlighted the mandatory need for the system to achieve high CMRR to dismiss common-mode interference. The electronics circuitry interfacing the electrodes has

to exhibit a high input impedance level to minimize the amplifier gain attenuation, avoiding loading error which might occur if the electrode and the front-end electronics input have an impedance mismatch. The common architecture to amplify small-scale signal amplitude and filter the interference with narrow bandwidth might be in the form of simple cascaded low-noise amplifiers. To block input DC offset, which might add some interference from the power supply, an inverting operational amplifier might be capacitively coupled with capacitors to eliminate the input DC offset. The first stage in front-end electronics directly interfacing electrodes is the most significant block, affecting the following stages. Therefore, the first block has to amplify the designated signal sufficiently without amplifying the noise and interference at the same time. [90]

In biomedical instrumentation, particularly the ultra-low amplitude in extracellular electrophysiology recording, a few sources of factors significantly affect the signal quality, such as common-mode interference, electrode-islet interface impedance, and instrumentation errors. Common-mode signals are a significant source of error where it arises when the common-mode interferences are transformed into differential signals following the op-amp. To mitigate common-mode interference, the practical solution is to employ an instrumentation amplifier (IA), which integrates feedback resistors with precise matching values connected to additional gain resistors to achieve a high CMRR value. Such a strategy achieves a high CMRR value as the input impedance to the amplifier is equal for both inputs to reduce the common-mode interference.

In the context of the flicker noise, the noise is related to the transistors, which also affects the overall noise, offset, and drift parameters from the IA. Flicker noise itself, commonly addressed as $1/f$ noise, is the major electronic noise in transistors due to the small active area dimension, where the noise is predominant in low-frequency signals. Therefore, in choosing the active component, paying attention to the $1/f$ corner frequency is important, with a preference toward the lower values. Besides the flicker noise, thermal noise also exhibited the noise contribution. Still, it is quite insignificant if the signal of interest lies in the low-frequency bandwidth with low electrical current.

From the defined requirement, in terms of the system integration, the electrode impedance should be lower than the input impedance of the front-end electronics to

avoid loading errors, which might be realised by employing as high as possible input impedance on the first stage of the front-end electronics. On the other hand, the input impedance of the analog circuitry has to match the high-impedance electrode to get maximum signal power transfer.

Most interference, such as those from the 50 Hz power line and its harmonics or surrounding lighting appliances, contribute greatly to signal quality. Proper grounding and shielding in the system are highly preferred as they drastically minimise electromagnetic interference (EMI). External EMI effect could be minimised by employing shielded closure, such as the standard Faraday cage, where the power supply voltage and input-output signals are routed to the system while blocking the sources of interference. It is important to transmit the I/O signals through properly shielded and grounded cables, mostly with BNC sockets on a grounded enclosure case. In certain cases, the incubator might behave as a Faraday cage, shielding the internal environment from external EMI and background noise.

Extracellular recording has a much lower voltage amplitude compared to intracellular electrophysiology. The low signal properties combined with affected signal quality by external background noise and interference might be handled by employing robust front-end electronics in the acquisition system to amplify the true signals further and attenuate the background noise and interference. To achieve the required time resolution of effectively capturing the short AP spikes, a minimal 1 kHz per electrode sampling rate is commonly employed, which translates into 7.5×10^{10} bits per second, assuming that 1 bit per cell would be sampled. To distinguish the cell source based on their spike shapes from the acquired signals, which typically record multiple cells simultaneously, electrophysiology recording systems generally employ a higher sampling rate ranging from 10 to 40 kHz. In extracellular neuron recording, it is assumed that one bit per neuron with sampling rate at 1 kHz is insufficient to distinguish spikes above existing noise. Therefore, transmitting 10-bit samples at 10 kHz full waveform, or in other words, 10-20 bits time stamps upon AP spike detection, is more realistic to fulfill the requirement. [91]

The sampling rate of 20 kHz in most electrophysiology systems is deemed enough for most applications. However, a major issue arises when choosing between tailoring the system for the high-frequency spikes without attenuating the important low-frequency signal components. It would be a straightforward process to simply apply HPF at a 300

Hz cutoff to acquire AP signals, but it has a detrimental effect on the synchronous low-frequency signals. [92]

A troubleshooting investigation of extracellular recording has been performed on a study involving neuronal culture with MEA. In that specific case, the cells have to be cultured 2-3 weeks prior to recording to reach a steady state of spontaneous AP, and the culture-wide AP bursts synaptically across the whole culture. When no AP activity is observed during the recording, the protocol is mentioned to ensure the culture age is sufficient and the cells are still alive. Afterward, the electrode impedance has to be checked, with a normal value between 100 Ω to 100 k Ω at 1 kHz, with a higher range indicating damaged electrodes or path and lower impedance reflecting insulation leak. The cortical network also has reduced activities when exposed to lower temperatures or no activities at all if the recording was performed after recent feeding or medium change. When excessive background noise occurs and saturates the recording amplitude, the contact between front-end electronics and the electrodes has to be ensured on both the damage on the electrode or insulation and their contact pads. Grounding also produces similar events, with all electrode signals presenting a highly noisy background when the system and connected cabling are not properly grounded and shielded. [81]

2.10 Signal Processing

In processing sensitive biomedical and biological signals with low amplitude, mathematical transformations such as Fourier transform (FT), and Wavelet transform (WT) are two of the most employed signal processing algorithms. While FT has great applicability to perform analysis on the frequency domain by converting the time-domain signals, it has challenges with the resolution and uncertainty of time-frequency representation. For this reason, WT has been more popular due to its robustness in performing signal denoising with varying noise and artefacts. WT works by deconstructing the original signal into different frequency components using some wavelet functions, sometimes also called the mother wavelet. The mother wavelet acts as a window moving forward along the time, decomposing the signals into a weighted set of scaled wavelet functions. Denoising with WT is particularly relevant in biomedical signals, such as ECG and EEG, which are often acquired along the noise from the subjects' movements or electrode and power line interference. Similar to

extracellular electrophysiology signals, ECG and EEG have weak amplitudes that are susceptible to amplified noise in the acquired recording. The SNR might be elevated by employing dynamic filtering, particularly with WT. [12] WT denoising involves different processing starting from the signal decomposition, zeroing, or thresholding according to the detail coefficients, and finally followed by the signal reconstruction with both the original approximation coefficients and the modified detail coefficients. [93]

Other than the mother wavelets selection, the thresholding method also crucially matters in the denoising process. Hard thresholding sets the coefficients to zero when the absolute values are lower than the threshold, while soft thresholding reduces the coefficients repetitively when they exceed the threshold by the threshold value itself. Soft thresholding, therefore, requires higher computation, but it generally produces better denoising performance. The decision between hard and soft thresholding, as well as global or local thresholding, also depends on specific patterns or requirements on the signal types. [93]

An adaptive threshold is specifically preferred considering dynamic signals, which cannot be discriminated with static/fixed thresholds considering the signal variations, especially in noisy signals. It is possible to perform a denoising process by simply removing the noise from the true signal, given that the noise characteristic is known and their pattern is recognisable to be subtracted. However, this is mostly not the case and not as straightforward in biological measurement, where various noise restraints efficient denoising. Yet, to counteract that argument, most existing noise in a one-dimensional transient signal follows Gaussian distribution, where the Bayes estimator might be used to optimize the denoising performance. In Wavelet denoising, the thresholding estimator utilised in orthogonal decomposition with multiresolution analysis and wavelet packet transform, where the parameter in Wavelet thresholding involves the thresholding method (either hard or soft) and the value dynamic (fixed or adaptive). Furthermore, the chosen wavelets themselves are also very crucial, as WT typically has multiple non-zero coefficients to describe the signals. Optimal wavelet with matching features, such as their vanishing moment and the size of the support, is highly correlated with the signal's regularity and the degree of noise present in the whole data. An increased non-zero coefficient in the noise removal process would significantly increase the computing complexity, therefore, selecting the optimised wavelet according to the signals of interest would provide more coefficients close to

zero and minimise the computational cost. In some cases involving pulse or sinusoidal signals, the magnitude of the coefficient might be reduced by implementing soft thresholding, while oscillation or ripples on the reconstructed signals result from hard thresholding. [94]

A vast amount of different mother wavelet functions are available to define how they scale the signals and determine the final waveform shape, such as Haar, Daubechies, Coiflets, Symlet, Biorthogonal, or Dmey, with different performances depending on each case. [93, 95, 96] Similar to FT, decomposed waveforms in WT typically have sinusoidal characteristics. In certain signal shape recognition, the WT was performed on noisy signals to produce a noise wavelet coefficient, combined with thresholding algorithms to remove the noise subsequently. Once the thresholding criteria have been established, the thresholded wavelet coefficient would then be processed with inverse WT, where the denoised signal is later reconstructed. [95]

Real-time detection of AP was enabled by adaptive threshold, combined with discrete Wavelet transform (DWT) and stationary Wavelet transform (SWT). The algorithm was developed to evaluate the AP detection rate and the computational cost to perform the detection involving a comparison of dynamically adapting threshold proportional to standard deviation (SD) implemented for online AP detection. [97] In the other study, spike detection was performed by multiple signal decomposition using appropriate wavelets to separate the signal from existing noise. Bayesian hypothesis was performed at different scales to detect the spike presence, where the decision on different scales would be combined later on to estimate the spike's arrival times. The background noise was assumed to be stationary or Gaussian noise, which resonates with the common assumption of noise in one-dimensional transient signals. [98]

AP detection algorithms are commonly employed with preprocessing algorithms to define AP shape after the noise outside the signal bandwidth has been attenuated. SWT with adaptive threshold is the common combination as time-frequency analysis based on filter bank decomposition on an orthogonal basis by convoluting the signals and the filters defining the mother wavelet. As mentioned before, signal parameters would be defined by the mother wavelet, sampling frequency, duration of the target event, and the level of detail to sustain. To perform the high computation process, field-programmable gate arrays (FPGA) are commonly utilised to execute the whole signal processing blocks online, such as defining and calculating the wavelet coefficients,

performing SWT, computing adaptive threshold, and applying the thresholding process, detecting the event, and eventually displaying the processed signals. [96] Preview of some signal processing algorithms implemented on some extracellular electrophysiology studies are described in Table 2.10.1.

Table 2.10.1: Signal Processing Algorithms Strategy in Extracellular Electrophysiology Platform

Algorithm	Details	Ref.
Wavelet Filter	AP detection with SWT Haar wavelets and adaptive thresholding at 2SD on sixth wavelet decomposition, with computation on AP average frequency, plateau fraction, and ratio of burst period. SP processing with second-order LPF Butterworth at 1 Hz cut-off frequency.	[50]
Spike Detection	Signals in the frequency range of 10-1000 Hz forwarded to the thresholding function with $6 \times$ SD and 40 ms dead time, with Wavelet transforms for feature extraction, including the centering, denoising, smoothing, focusing, and online adaptive thresholding based on live SD.	[51]
MEA2100 Use Case	HPF at 200 Hz and LPF at 4 kHz, with 25 kHz sampling rate and spike thresholding at $10 \times$ SD of noise.	[52]
MC Rack Software (MCS)	SP detection with 0.2-2 Hz second-order Butterworth IIR filter combined with threshold module at 300 ms dead time. SP amplitude is inferred from the amplitude of the filtered signal's envelope.	[58]
AP and SP Detection	AP are processed by bandpass Butterworth filter, with adaptive thresholding at $2.9 \times$ SD and digital blanking for 75 ms. SP is detected with third-order bandpass filtering at 0.1-1 Hz bandwidth and amplitude tolerance of 8 μ V.	[13]
System Architecture	Real-time processing for AP, SP, LFP, and bursts with Butterworth IIR filter for SP signals, wavelet filter for AP detection, SD estimator for adaptive thresholding, and two-threshold comparator for event detection.	[54]

Besides event detection, the extracellular electrophysiology platform also benefits from the electrode sorting module, which rules out the non-functioning electrodes from the subsequent digital processing and reduces the overall computation cost. The electrodes uncovered by the cells or organoids can be identified by comparing the averaged normal behavior embedded with the designated signals. Besides lowering the computation cost, such an algorithm would also result in more reliable data as the functioning electrodes only fulfill the statistical contribution. [99]

Aside from digital discrimination of non-functioning electrodes, the hardware approach employs crosstalk detection by recording voltage transients from electrodes around selected ones with delivered constant current to monitor their current leakage. By definition, crosstalk occurs when some signal coupling representing current leakage between different electrode channels happens, mostly due to physical damage on the electrode, such as corrosion or crack, as well as a delaminated passivating layer. To read their impedance change, AC impedance spectroscopy can also be done to trace connection failure. However, it is mostly detectable once the physical failure is already damaging enough. The reported study also managed to perform a charge injection test to distinguish open-circuit signals. [100]

Spike detection and sorting algorithms recently faced huge issues with scalability, with high-density electrodes reaching up to thousands of electrodes in the system, which exponentially increases the computation cost, hindering efficient data processing in the measurement. Some toolboxes have been developed to perform density-based clustering and template matching to detect AP with threshold crossing detection and isolating AP. The performance is further enhanced by training non-linear classifiers on the ground truth data, with the classifiers finding true spikes among the false positive and false negative spikes. [101]

High noise amplitude and non-stationary issues in AP spike detection might be tackled by filtering in the preprocessing stage with optimised filter parameters. However, fixed parameters are not efficient enough with dynamic artefacts and noise. Empirical mode decomposition can be used to set the filter parameters dynamically automatically, as spike detection is a signal-dependent signal with performance highly dependent on it. Additionally, fuzzy set theory to combine a number of spike detectors can also be utilised to increase AP spike detection performance. [102]

Chapter 3

Methodology

The research methodology subsection in the first chapter has provided an overview of the implemented research method in the project. Details on each subsystem, both in the experimental design and execution, to the interpretations of the result will be described in this chapter.

3.1 Design Philosophy and Rationale

3.1.1 Islet Trapping Mechanism

The primary function of the microfluidic device is to support the electrophysiology recording with the microelectrode array subsystem. This is achieved by positioning the islets on top of the electrodes, thereby optimising the contact interface between the electrodes and the intact islets. The microfluidic platform is designed to automatically load islets into the trapping sites, deliver nutrients, and provide continuous GSIS stimulation. In detail, the microfluidic platform has the requirement to facilitate automatic islet loading to the trapping sites, nutrient delivery, and continuous GSIS stimulation. Holding on to those considerations, the trapping mechanism has to provide the immobilisation mechanism without exposing the islets to mechanical stress and count for the 3D structure.

Hydrodynamic trapping immobilises particles with a specific size range by using the principle of flow resistance difference between the main channel and the trapping site region. The chosen trapping strategy is passive hydrodynamic trapping with microfiltration arrays, adapted by a trap-and-release mechanism developed by Tan and

Takeuchi. [63] In this project, U-shaped trapping based on passive hydrodynamics microfiltration is utilised to retain pressure-driven flow as the trapping mechanism. The U-cup shape is chosen for better conformality in trapping the spherical shape of the pancreatic islet, compared to the other geometries. In order to trap the islets sequentially, the crossflow technique is implemented in the trapping system, which consists of a bypass channel with several trapping sites.

The U-cup trapping sites are positioned along the bypass channel, and they are defined by tight side-wall apertures to target the islets' flows into the trapping site. At the main channel intersection leading to the trapping site, the lower flow resistance in the trapping site than the main channel would cause the islets to prefer to flow towards the vacant trapping site. Once an islet occupies the trapping site, the flow resistance at the trapping site would then rise, redirecting subsequent islets to flow along the channel, bypassing the occupied site, and moving to the next trap site instead. With reduced hydrodynamic resistance around the trapping site when the islet fills it, the trapping mechanism prevents shear-induced damage to islets that could compromise their morphology and functionality by restricting the flow rate around the trapped islets. Nevertheless, the stagnant flow around the trapping site still allows the delivery of nutrients and stimulants-containing medium from the fluidic flow.

3.1.2 Microfluidic Design

To achieve the goals, single-islet arraying with hydrodynamic trapping in a microfluidic chip is designed with several considerations. In order to successfully trap islets, the flow rate at the trapping site is required to be higher than in the main channel, with an optimum flow resistance ratio of $Q_{\text{trapsite}}/Q_{\text{mainchannel}}$. Furthermore, the height of the channel should accommodate most of the islet's diameter while not being too tall either to minimise the vertical gap to the electrode interface.

To meet the design constraint, the U-cup-shaped trapping sites are designed with an opening width of 250 μm and 312 μm distance to the aperture. At the deep end of each trapping site, the U-cup opening is then reduced from the 250 μm opening to 45 μm , creating the aperture gap to provide the required flow resistance ratio. The trapping site and main channel dimension are shown in Figure 3.1.1.

In addition to the aperture at the deep end of the trapping site, some of the trapping arrays are modified with an intercavity connection to facilitate islet communication.

Figure 3.1.1: Design of the microfluidic device with single main channel and double islet trapping sites.

This feature was planned to be utilized to observe islet-to-islet interaction. However, it was not pursued further for this project. The microfluidic design variation is shown in Figure 3.1.2.

In the first proof-of-test, the channel was designed with 9 rows of trapping site array. The final design reduced the number to 5 rows of trapping site array, with the U-cup and aperture dimensions remaining unchanged. Previously, some designs involved branching main channels from the inlet to increase the number of trapping sites and the experiment throughput, but it was further simplified into a single serpentine main channel to reduce the complexity. While the single and double U-cup trapping sites were set as the primary focus of the project, triple U-cup sites were also prepared as backups. The inclusion of double and triple trapping sites, connected internally, was specifically intended for advanced islet-islet interaction studies. This aspect of the design aimed to investigate whether closely positioned islets would synchronise in response to glucose stimuli and to evaluate the potential islet-islet vascularisation effect on their summative behavior in physiological conditions.

3.1.3 Electrode Design

The recording electrode interfacing the islets was designed with diameters of 30 and 50 μm , close to the orifice in the trapping site. Meanwhile, the reference electrode is designed with 160 μm width and 1660 μm length, located in the straight main channel

Figure 3.1.2: Design variation of the microfluidic device.

close to the inlet. The chosen diameters refer to the standard commercial electrodes for extracellular recording in islets. The recording electrode placement on the trapping site aperture end was chosen based on the previously tested islet trapping behavior.

To determine the optimal alignment of electrodes with the trapping sites, the focus is paid to the most commonly occupied areas by the trapped islets, regardless of the diameter. The islets tend to be pushed away to the aperture end, thus used as the basis of the maximum area that is always occupied by the islets. A much larger reference electrode was placed along the inlet main channel with $160\ \mu\text{m}$ width, considering the fluidic main channel width of $300\ \mu\text{m}$ to provide room for misalignment during manual integration. The interconnection to the recording electrode was designed with a width of $5\ \mu\text{m}$ and extended to a larger $20\ \mu\text{m}$ width to the $200 \times 200\ \mu\text{m}$ contact pad. The design layout of the recording and reference electrode is shown in Figure 3.1.3.

The interconnection path layout between the medium-interfacing electrodes and contact pads was made considering the passivation layer. The devices were divided into two types of passivation; the first one was designed for the electrode to be immediately bonded to PDMS without an additional insulating layer on the electrode. The path was thus made to avoid exposing them to the electrolyte in the medium, which

Figure 3.1.3: Design preview of the microelectrodes with respect to the microfluidic design.

requires them to take over the part outside the fluidic channel and trapping site. The second type was designed for insulated electrodes. Therefore, it only requires a more simplified design as long as both electrodes and the contact pads are connected.

3.1.4 Photomasks for Device Fabrication

Initially, the microfluidic channel, microelectrode arrays, and passivation patterns are designed in computer-aided design (CAD) software, specifically SolidWorks, with the aforementioned design considerations and with respect to their alignment as the individual design of the designs are then converted into DXF files compatible with KLayout, a common software to design lithography mask layout patterns, to finalize the photomask layout design and sent to the manufacturer creating the photomasks, which are utilised during the photolithography step during cleanroom fabrication.

The design layouts were drawn on SolidWorks first, instead of performing the whole design immediately on KLayout, considering the intuitive tools and more features available. In the microfluidic channel design, for example, it is difficult to employ and manipulate curves or other rounded geometries on KLayout, which is highly needed to minimise the fluidic turbulence at sharp angles and corners. The coordinate-centric design approach on KLayout also makes it difficult to move the structures, especially when aligning different layers altogether. SolidWorks provides parametric design

features, allowing iterations of the drawn structures simply to make them uniform or just to do modification by simply copying them and changing the geometrical parameters (for example, the diameter of a circle), which is not feasible on KLayout so far.

Figure 3.1.4: Devices configuration and the photomasks.

The KLayout design, however, is still needed to perform mask layout optimisation, ensuring and adjusting the patterning layouts, which the aim objective commonly is to edit IC layout designs, and it is useful when the design creation has been done in SolidWorks prior. SolidWorks is not specifically accustomed to performing 2D design better than KLayout as a dedicated 2D layout editor. The operation between layers, including the overall pattern alignment, is much better in KLayout, which is also important to ensure alignment precision or simply employ certain alignment marks. Moreover, the photomask production also prefers the GDSII format, which KLayout produces but not SolidWorks. The basic configuration of the device is represented in Figure 3.1.4, while the previews of the mask design variation are shown in Figure 3.1.5.

The optical photomasks were ordered from a manufacturer (JD Photodata, UK) to be used during UV exposure to the photoresist during the photolithography process in cleanroom fabrication. The pattern is printed on Agfa Idealine High-Resolution Plotter Film (HPF), which is a 0.18 mm thick polyester PET film and soft photographic emulsion gel coating conforming the pattern on one side, with a total surface area

	With Insulator		Without Insulator	
	50 μm	30 μm	50 μm	30 μm
Microfluidic A				
Microfluidic B				
Microfluidic C				
Microfluidic D				

Figure 3.1.5: Design variation of the photomasks

of 12×18 inch (205×280 mm) and 9×12 inch (280×430 mm). Each of the devices has a dimension of 10.3×13.9 mm. The printing resolution of each of the masks has to be matched to how crucial their design fidelity is. As the structural pattern is still achievable with a low-resolution approach using the film photomasks, the glass photomasks are avoided to match the budget allocation. The photomasks for all three layers are designed as negative tone, with 25 μm line resolution (grade 2 resolution) for the microfluidic and passivation photomasks as their smallest feature are 45 μm , and 5 μm (grade 4 resolution) for the electrode one with also 5 μm of the smallest feature.

3.1.5 Front-end Electronics Design

The overall signal acquisition system function is achieved by combining the front-end electronics, analog to digital converter (ADC), and digital interface from the oscilloscope to visualise the non-processed data and convert the analog front-end signals into digital back-end stage, and lastly, the offline signal conditioning. The front-end electronics block is divided into an instrument amplifier block, followed by the amplifying high-pass and low-pass filter stage, as shown in Figure 3.1.6. Conversion of the analog signal into a digital one was performed at the digital oscilloscope, Moku:Go, which has an ADC with 12-bit resolution and 125 MSa/s sampling rate. The input impedance is 1 M Ω with a range of 10 or 50 V_{pp}. The oscilloscope also has an arbitrary waveform generator and spectrum analyser, which can generate sinusoidal waves up to 20 MHz. [103]

Figure 3.1.6: Signal acquisition block diagram.

Design specifications, such as the required amplification and filter bandwidth, were acquired from relevant references found during the initial literature review stage. It is important to achieve the high amplification and proper filter bandwidth in the system, which leads to the main requirement of achieving $\pm 1100 \times$ gain and 0.1-3000 Hz bandwidth to acquire the signals. The topology and circuit design were optimized to maximize the amplification and filter performance, with standard biomedical electronics principles as consideration.

As the magnitudes of the expected signals are in the microvolt range, a quite high signal amplification is needed so that the oscilloscope may capture the signals in higher amplitudes. Several stages of low- and high-pass filters are needed to reduce the undesired noise and interference into several magnitudes lower and distinguish them from the true signals. Aside from the operational amplifier to employ the needed gain and filters, the front-end electronics also include instrumentation amplifiers (IA) as the first block interfacing the electrodes with high CMRR to reject the common-mode interference. The recorded analog signals from the islets are converted into

digital signals by the ADC within the oscilloscope following the amplification and filters. The combination of different analog signal processing in this subsystem produces the raw analog signal to be processed in the digital block without deforming the electrophysiology signals. Input and output access, as well as the bypass capacitors and power supply schematic, are shown in Figure 3.1.7

Figure 3.1.7: Schematic of signal input-output, power supply, and bypass capacitors.

Considering the low-amplitude signals in AP and SP, parasitic leakage current and voltage disturbance from the components and circuitry play a major role in generating interpretable signals. The analog front-end circuitry, therefore, has to employ active components with very low input-referred noise. Precision op-amps with low input bias current and low voltage noise are ideal for choosing the op-amps for the filter amplifiers. Meanwhile, low input noise and high input impedance were the main parameters in choosing the IA. The important parameters for choosing the active components include the input voltage noise, offset tolerance, and common-mode rejection ratio.

Electrode offset comes from different potentials between electrodes that might cause the electrode to saturate over the ADC dynamic range after amplification. The input voltage noise was aimed to be lower than $1 \mu\text{Vpp}$ according to the intended signal amplitude range. It should also hold out against the electrode offset and present a high CMRR of at least 100 dB. Two 9 V batteries supplied the power for the front-end electronics to avoid interference from the power line while providing a dual supply to produce a larger output voltage range.

The first stage is utilising INA821 (Texas Instruments) instrumentation amplifier with

35 μV offset voltage and 7 $\text{nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ input-referred noise. The IA topology consists of three op-amps, with two of those acting as buffers to supply high differential and unity gain to provide high input impedance and low output resistance. By matching the value of feedback resistors, the following differential amplifier would have a high CMRR from the resistor divider network. Furthermore, as CMRR refers to the ratio of differential gain to common mode gain, implementing the gain prior to the differential amplifier would enhance the CMRR. The principle explains why INA821 presents 105 dB of CMRR with $1\times$ gain, while the value will be 125 dB when used with $10\times$ gain. Schematic of INA821 is shown in Figure 3.1.8.

Figure 3.1.8: Simplified internal schematic of INA821 instrumentation amplifier from Texas Instruments datasheet. [104]

To mitigate electrode offset, an AC-coupled amplifier is chosen as the topology. The capacitor coupled to the input would behave as a high-pass filter, removing DC offset with passive RC at the differential amplifier. CMRR is highly affected by electrode impedance or gain mismatch, where both can be limited by increasing the interfacing amplifier's input impedance and implementing common mode feedforward, canceling the common mode current. To improve the input impedance of the amplifier, the non-inverting amplifier is the most utilised topology, combined with impedance bootstrapping and positive voltage feedback to the amplifier.

Signal behaviour from the circuit was analysed through LTspice simulation to acquire the simulation results. Proper circuit design was ensured by simulating the signals before ordering the readily assembled board. The PCB board and components were ordered from JLCPCB and delivered in the form of assembled boards ready to use. The

calculation for the passive components was done using filter wizard tools from Analog Devices, where the design was performed at EasyEDA software, and overall simulation of the implemented design was done with LTspice prior to sending the design to be ordered from an industrial manufacturer.

The passive components, capacitors and resistors were calculated with 5% capacitor tolerance and 1% resistor tolerance, as well as taking the 20% gain bandwidth product (GBW) into account and utilizing the E24 series. For the simulation, AC sweep analysis from 10 MHz to 100 kHz was done to observe the frequency response to validate the design, focusing on their gain magnitude and filter response at their respective frequencies. The implemented front-end electronics frequency response was also checked with a digital oscilloscope and compared to the simulation result. Meanwhile, the voltage response was assessed by injecting a 10 mV_{pp} sinusoidal wave at 100 Hz at the input and observed both the simulated and the real output voltage response. Preview of the implemented design and the PCB layout are shown in Figure 3.1.9.

Figure 3.1.9: Front-end electronic schematic design and PCB layout.

A higher filter order would generally result in a more stable system with less ripple and a better damping response. Therefore, instead of implementing an immediate bandpass filter, which presents an appalling slope in the filter response, the blocks are divided into HPF and LPF blocks individually. Both the HPF and LPF blocks are designed each with $10.5\times$ or 20.4 dB active gain, with cutoff and stopband frequency at 0.1 Hz and 0.01 Hz for HPF, as well as 3 kHz and 10 kHz for LPF, respectively. Two quad-precision operational amplifiers OPAOPA4197IPWR (Texas Instruments), are used for HPF and LPF block on each channel. The op-amp has 100 μ V offset

voltage, $55 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ input-referred noise, and 120 dB CMRR, which all meet the design requirement. Combined with the initial $10\times$ or 20 dB gain from the IA block, the overall system is expected to meet $1100\times$ or 60.8 dB gain with $0.1\text{-}3000 \text{ Hz}$ filter bandwidth.

The HPF block was implemented with the third order Butterworth filter consisting of two stages, with the first stage of the first order buffered RC passive filter and the second stage of the second order Sallen Key active filter. The buffered RC was designed to support $\pm 10\times$ gain and $\pm 99 \text{ mHz}$ cutoff, and the Sallen Key was defined with $\pm 1.02\times$ gain and $\pm 99 \text{ mHz}$ cutoff. Afterward, the LPF block was implemented with a 4th-order Butterworth filter instead, with both two stages of the 2nd-order Sallen Key active filter. The first stage was designed with $\pm 42.4\times$ gain and $\pm 3 \text{ kHz}$ cutoff, meanwhile, the second one has $\pm 2.1\times$ gain and $\pm 3 \text{ kHz}$ cutoff.

3.2 Fabrication and Assembly

3.2.1 Cleanroom Fabrication

The microfabrication on the microfluidic masters and microelectrode arrays was performed in the KTH Electrum Laboratory cleanroom to ensure dust-free conditions. The cleanroom fabrication consisted of the fabrication of a silicon wafer to create the microfluidic master, gold deposition on a glass wafer to create the electrodes, deposition of SU-8 passivation layer on some of the electrodes, and wafer dicing. Selective patterning of the photoresist layer during the etching, lift-off, and development was performed through standard photolithography procedures with UV light exposure, while the electrodes were fabricated with electron-beam evaporation and standard lift-off techniques.

Otherwise mentioned differently, all the spin coating processes were done with a default setup incorporating an initial speed of 500 RPM for 5 seconds, followed by 3000 RPM for 30 seconds (LabSpin8, SUSS MicroTec). The exposure was performed under a 350 W UV mercury lamp with a 405 nm wavelength and $20 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$ intensity in the mask aligner (MA6/BA6 Mask Aligner, Karl Suss).

The mask aligner has a 6×6 -inch holder compatible with both 6-inch diameter silicon and glass wafers utilised in the project. As the holder is suitable for holding low-reflection chrome oxide on a 3 mm thick glass photomask, meanwhile photomasks

for the project were made on PET film, an unused chrome photomask available in the cleanroom was cleaned off using chromium etchant and acetone to remove the residues. The respective PET photomask was then adhered to the blank glass with scotch tape for the UV exposure step. The number of wafers to be fabricated was prepared with some spares as dummies to find the right fabrication settings and profiles.

3.2.1.1 Microfluidic Silicon Master Mold Template

The microfluidic device master for soft lithography was fabricated on a 6-inch diameter and 1 mm thick silicon wafer by etching through the surface with deep reactive ion etching (DRIE), as presented in Figure 3.2.1. The wafer was initially treated with hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) and dehydrated at 150° C to remove any moisture.

Figure 3.2.1: Process flow of microfluidics mold template fabrication.

The photomask was used to create the etch pattern through photolithography on the spin-coated photoresist with a negative tone mask, and the pattern was transferred using a positive photoresist. Following a spin coat of 3 μm positive deep dry etching resist ((TCIR-ZR8800, Tokyo Ohka Kogyo), the silicon wafers were soft baked on a hotplate at 130° C for 90 seconds to ensure the spin-coated resist uniformity and then exposed to 365 nm wavelength UV light with 400 mJ/cm² dose using mask aligner on hard contact mode for 20 seconds to crosslink the resist. Following the exposure, the wafers were soft-baked at 110° C for 1 minute and developed using an alkaline developer (MF-CD26, Microposit) at 21° C for 2 minutes.

Anisotropic etching was performed through deep reactive-ion etching on inductively coupled plasma (ICP) for 2 hours to produce a high aspect ratio etching of the silicon mold of 310 μm height (ICP-DRIE, STS). The etched silicon thickness and profile were measured using a mechanical profilometer (DektakXT, Bruker), where the aimed etch depth was validated, with ±320-400 μm etch profile observed. The remaining resist

was then stripped in oxygen plasma with a 500 ml/minute oxygen flow rate and 1000 W power for 10 minutes (Tepla 300, Tepla). Thin polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) coating with carbon fluoride C₄F₈ was performed under vacuum using ICP at 100 S/cm on 300 W power for 30 seconds to provide a Teflon layer supporting PDMS detachment from the silicon mold later on during soft lithography. As a final step, the wafer was diced into three parts to fit in the 150 mm dish for PDMS fabrication.

3.2.1.2 Planar Gold Electrodes

To support optical inspection during islet loading and recording from a stereomicroscope and inverted microscope, the electrodes are fabricated on transparent 6-inch glass wafers and SU-8 layer as the insulation layer. The recording electrode site, contact pad, and the rest of the connecting path were fabricated with gold, while the SU-8 layer was sequentially deposited and aligned to the electrodes on some of the chip configurations. The fabrication was done with standard photolithography for patterning and lift-off metallization techniques for metal deposition, as shown in Figure 3.2.2.

Initially, a layer of lift-off resist (LOR 5A, Kayaku) and positive resist (AZ 4533, MicroChemicals GmbH) were both spin-coated sequentially onto the glass wafer at a pre-setup of 500 rpm for 5 seconds and then ramped up to 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. The spin-coated wafers were then hard baked at 170° C for 30 minutes for the lift-off resist and 90° C for 10 minutes for the positive resist, instead of soft bake on a hotplate, to avoid resist bends from the glass bending. The wafers were then exposed to 365 nm wavelength UV light with 300 mJ/cm² dose for 15 seconds using a mask aligner on hard contact mode with an alignment gap between the sample and the mask of 20 μm. The wafers were developed after the exposure with the appropriate developer (MF-CD26, Microposit).

After the photoresist patterning step, electron-beam evaporation was performed to pattern the metal layer (PAK 600 Coating System, Provac). Prior to evaporation, the wafers were rinsed dry with a spin rinse dryer (Semitool 870S, Sitek). Six photoresist-coated glass wafers were placed accordingly to ensure uniform sputtering, with setup to achieve 200 nm of gold layer and 2 nm of titanium layer underneath to enhance gold layer adhesion on the glass wafer. Afterward, the lift-off resist was stripped in a remover solution (Remover PG, MicroChem) for 2 hours to define the gold

Figure 3.2.2: Process flow of microelectrodes array fabrication.

interconnects and electrodes. The wafers were spin rinse dried at 1400 rpm and dehydrated in a 180°C oven. The fabrication step was wrapped up in this stage for the electrode configuration without the SU-8 passivation layer and finalised by coating positive resist as a protective layer and dice the wafers, while the rest of them were further processed in the following step.

For the SU-8 insulated electrode configuration, the electrode wafers were spin-coated with SU-8 2002 (MicroChem Corporation) using the default setup and followed by a pre-exposure bake at 95°C for 1 minute on a hotplate to solidify 2 μm thick uniform SU-8 layer on the top surface. The 365 nm I-line bandpass filter was used with the mask aligner to expose the SU-8 at the recommended wavelength. The recommended exposure energy for 2 μm thickness is 80 mJ/cm^2 exposure dose, which should be increased $1.5\times$ to 120 mJ/cm^2 dose, counting on their consideration of exposure on the glass substrate. Precise passivation mask and gold-coated wafer alignment were performed using the mask aligner, with a hard contact of 20 μm alignment gap and optimised on 25 seconds exposure time to the 365 nm wavelength UV light with approximately 240 mJ/cm^2 exposure dose (MA6/BA6 Mask Aligner, Karl Suss). A post-exposure bake was then performed to further crosslink SU-8 on a hotplate at 95°C for 2 minutes. The wafers were developed by submerging them in developer solution (mr-Dev 600, MicroResist) for 70 seconds and in isopropyl alcohol (IPA) for 10 seconds to dissolve the unpolymersed SU-8. The wafers were then dried with nitrogen gas and finally dehydrated at 1000 rpm and spun dry for 1 minute.

As a protective layer to the electrodes, 4 μm of positive resist (AZ 4533, MicroChemicals GmbH) was spin-coated and hard baked at 110°C for 2 minutes without the exposure

and development step. Prior to utilization, the protective layer on the electrode can be dissolved by immersion in acetone. The finalized electrode wafers were adhered to blue tape on the bottom side for dicing and then diced into smaller devices with individual chip dimensions of 1.03×1.39 mm die pieces based on the respective cutting mark using automatic dicing saw (DAD 3241, Disco Corporation). The cut was performed with 0.045 mm height, 1 mm/s feed speed, and spindle revolution of 30,000 rpm with 0.25 ± 0.001 mm thick, 40 mm inner diameter, and 58 mm outer diameter cutting blade (DISCO Diamond Blade Z05-SD1200-D1-60, Disco Corporation).

3.2.2 Non-Cleanroom Fabrication

3.2.2.1 Microfluidic Fabrication

The microfluidic devices were fabricated using soft lithography at non-cleanroom MST Laboratory and Scilifelab Laboratory, using silicon masters previously fabricated in the cleanroom. A mixture of PDMS elastomer base and curing agent (Slygard 184, Dow Corning) was prepared with a 10:1 (w/w) ratio and mixed using a shaker for 2 minutes on 2500 revolutions per minute (RMP). The spun PDMS mixture was initially degassed in a desiccator for 5 minutes and subsequently poured directly on top of the silicon master with an etched feature facing up inside a 105 mm dish, after which it was further degassed for 1 hour. Afterward, the PDMS was cured in an oven at 80° C for 2 hours, then the polymerised PDMS pattern was cut and gently peeled off circumferentially from the dish side wall to leave the remaining unused PDMS on the silicon mold and reduce the amount of PDMS mixture to be poured into in the next fabrication. Preview of cured PDMS on the silicon mold template and their circumference peel-off are shown in Figure 3.2.3.

The 10×14 mm individually cut microfluidic chips were then punched with a 1.2 mm biopsy puncher to create holes on the inlet and outlet ports fitting 1.27 mm outer diameter of 18 gauge blunt tip or 1.24 mm outer diameter of 18G steel tubing to be connected with 0.8 mm inner diameter of tubing as the fluidic access. The PDMS chip was then bonded on top of a glass slide for the microfluidic test without electrodes or directly on top of the electrodes for integration of the complete device.

Figure 3.2.3: Cured PDMS and peeled off PDMS residues on silicon wafer mold template.

3.2.2.2 Microfluidic and Electrode Integration

In the assembly preparation, the photoresist protective layer on the electrode was initially washed off with immersion in acetone before the bonding process with PDMS. Prior to surface treatment and subsequent bonding, the PDMS and substrate surface were cleaned using scotch tape to ensure no dust contamination. The microfluidics and clean glass slide or electrode were then plasma-treated in a vacuum to activate their surface and render the PDMS hydrophilic at 5.5 W power and 0.8 mbar for 30 seconds (CUTE-1MP/R, Femto Science for oxygen plasma or Femto Plasma-Cleaner, Diener Electronic GmbH for air plasma). For PDMS bonding with a glass slide or electrode configuration without SU-8 passivation layer, the PDMS was immediately bonded to the electrode after the plasma treatment without further surface processing, while their bonding to SU-8 passivated electrode was followed by further silanisation with an organosilane layer.

Trials in application of (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES, Sigma Aldrich) was pursued in both liquid and gas phase to activate PDMS silanisation with SU-8 and ensure their tight seal, based on a publication by Ret et al. [105] In the liquid phase, 99% APTES was drop-casted on a glass slide on which the PDMS was then put over with the bonding interface facing the glass following the plasma treatment. After 5 minutes, the PDMS was washed with DI water and dried. On the other side, the vapor phase silanisation was done by placing the PDMS with the patterned feature facing up in a desiccator containing 99% APTES droplet on a glass slide in vacuum condition for 1 hour.

The alignment step with the electrode in the bonding process was performed manually by hand under live view with a stereomicroscope. The treated PDMS was carefully aligned on top of the electrode by gently holding it with a curved tip tweezer on the outer side wall from a vertical position. The aperture at the end of the U-cup trapping site was aligned to be parallel with the circular recording electrodes, combined with the other alignment references to the reference electrode in the inlet main channel and the rest of the parallel recording electrodes array. Following the surface activation, alignment, and bonding process, the integrated device was then cured at 122° C for 15 minutes. A simple fluidic pressure leakage test was then performed to evaluate PDMS bonding results and ensure the integrated device reliability by connecting both the inlet and outlet with tubings to a 3 mL syringe and introducing gentle fluid delivery from both sides by hand. If some leakage was immediately found, a pull test to separate bonded PDMS from the substrate was performed to find the leak spot and find out the causes.

3.2.2.3 Hardware System Integration

The electrode was initially attached to a slightly larger glass for easier handling with polyimide tape, where both of them were then subsequently attached to the connector board. Polyimide tape was utilised to adhere the bonded electrode to the glass slide and connector board instead of scotch tape to avoid their delamination during the application of the electrode contact connection using a conductive epoxy. PDMS was once utilised as the adhesive during pilot trials to assemble the glass and connector board. However, it significantly increases the assembly processing time since the PDMS needs to be cured first; therefore, the polyimide tape is a more time-efficient alternative.

To connect the contact pads of the electrode to contact probes on the board, silver conductive epoxy (CW2460, CircuitWorks) was utilised with a 1:1 mixture of the epoxy to the hardener. Prior to the application of the epoxy, the connector board surface was cleaned with acetone to remove potential contaminants that could affect the electrical properties. The applied epoxy, along with the PDMS, electrode, and connector board underneath, underwent a curing process at 120° C for 20 minutes to achieve optimal conductivity. According to their datasheet, CW2460 conductive epoxy has at least 75% composition of silver, with their volumetric resistivity less than 0.001 Ω-cm, corresponding to conductivity at least 0.001 S/cm.

3.3 Experimental Setup and Protocols

3.3.1 Pancreatic Islets Isolation and Culture

Pancreatic islets were isolated from adult mice at the Rofit Luft Centre, Karolinska Institutet. All experimental procedures were performed following the guideline on animal care and use in research from Karolinska Institutet, and the euthanasia and surgical procedures were carried out by a qualified research specialist authorised to conduct animal experiments. Adult wild-type mice from 8 to 10 weeks old were obtained from the breeding colony at Karolinska Institutet and euthanized by cervical dislocation. Prior to surgery, the abdominal fur was wetted with 70% alcohol to minimize exposure to contamination.

The incision on the abdominal region was made to expose the organs in the peritoneal cavity, and then the common bile duct (CBD) was cannulated close to the small intestine junction to restrict the buffer flow outward the pancreas on the following injection. The pancreas was distended by perfusion through the CBD with ice-cold collagenase P (1.5 mg.ml⁻¹, Roche) dissolved in Hanks' Balanced Salt Solution (HBSS) buffer supplemented with BSA (2.5 mg.ml⁻¹, Fisher) in HEPES (25 × 10⁻³ M, Gibco) and 7.4 pH. The pancreas should be inflated completely to ensure enough collagenase in all pancreas and maximize the isolation yield. Following the collagenase injection, the pancreas was removed from the intestines, liver, and spleen, then stored in an ice-cold HBSS washing buffer in a 15 mL conical tube to perform the digestion process.

The digestion steps were performed through enzymatic collagenase dissociation with gentle agitation in a 37° C water bath for 15 minutes. After the enzymatic digestion and passing through an 18G needle for further liberation, the islets were separated from the remaining exocrine tissue using 100 µm cell strainers while washing them with the HBSS buffer. The islets were then further purified by hand-picking under a stereomicroscope from the suspension culture to the ice-cold HBSS while being hand-picked to inhibit the digestion on the collagenased pancreas before incubation. The transfer from HBSS to RPMI culture medium has to be as immediate as possible, to reduce contamination risks and minimise pH differences that could stress the islets.

As a final step, the isolated islets were moved to the 60 × 15 mm suspension culture dishes containing 5 ml of RPMI 1640 solution (Gibco) with 10% (v/v) Fetal Bovine

Serum (FBS, Gibco), 1% Penicillin-Streptomycin consisted of 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 mg/mL streptomycin (Gibco), and 2 mM L-Glutamine (Gibco). The islets were cultured with a density of less than 70 islets in each dish to avoid nutrient competition and incubated for at least overnight at controlled conditions in a sterile incubator at 37° C with 5% CO₂ infusion and humidified air to let the islets recover from the stress from isolation procedure until use. The healthy islets to be recorded in the experiment were chosen based on their morphology and integrity by visual check under a microscope.

3.3.2 Microbeads or Islets Loading and Medium Perfusions

In the initial phase, hydrodynamic trapping experiments were conducted using 125-180 µm polyethylene microspheres (1.025 g.cc⁻¹, Cospheric) that reflected in the typical dimensions of islets. These experiments aimed to pre-analyse the feasibility of trapping particles on the chip. The inlet and outlet access were connected through 18G stainless steel tubing connectors matching the 0.5 mm inner diameter (ID) tubing. PTFE tubings were used to flow the fluidic medium through the inlet and outlet.

Before the experiment with beads or islets, the fluidic channel was initially perfused with absolute ethanol for 5 minutes to enhance the internal wettability. Subsequently, the medium (DI water for experiments with polyethylene beads or RPMI and physiological buffer for islets) flowed through the channel for at least 10 minutes. Both syringes on the outlet and inlet were then pushed simultaneously to introduce higher pressure in the inlet, diminishing the air bubble inside the fluidic channel.

Continuous fluidic control is controlled by a syringe pump connected to the outlet (NE-300, Just Infusion), with a constant flow of 70 µl/min, withdrawing the fluid reverse flow from the inlet to the outlet. The polyethylene beads or hand-picked islets were loaded directly into the inlet reservoir and delivered into the microfluidic channel by the negative pressure in the system. The reservoir is connected to the medium stock in a 30 mL syringe connected by the tubing, where the medium change is performed by simply replacing the whole syringe while clamping the tubing with a paperclip. The end of the outlet tubing was connected to a 30 mL syringe containing the waste, positioned with the tip on top to prevent contaminated waste from going back to the microfluidic channel in the experiment. During the operation, an inverted microscope or stereomicroscope observes the trapping mechanism of both

the polyethylene microspheres and islets. The hydrodynamically trapped islets or microspheres are released by reversing the fluid flow from the outlet to the inlet to collect the samples back at the reservoir at the end of the experiment.

3.3.3 Electrophysiology Recording Setup

Experiments with islets were conducted using the 11.1 mM glucose-containing RPMI medium or physiological buffer accustomed without phenol red. Physiological buffer mimicking extracellular solution was prepared by mixing 125 mM NaCl, 5.9 KCl, 2.56 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.2 mM $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 25 mM HEPES, and albumin 1 mg/ml in 100 mL Milli-Q ultrapure water. The buffer solution was then adjusted until 7.4 pH was reached by adding NaOH solution with a pH meter. Finally, D-glucose was added to create two separate solutions, one with a concentration of 3 mM and another with 11 mM. A solution with 25 mM KCl was also prepared with the physiological buffer.

Before conducting experiments, the islets were incubated for 1 hour in basal conditions of a physiological buffer containing 3 mM glucose, and then their basal activity was observed for 5-10 minutes to monitor the baseline response. This step is crucial for ensuring that the cells are stabilised before further experimentation. The glucose stimulation protocol typically involves shifting the basal 3 mM glucose after being observed for 5 minutes, then introducing the 11 mM glucose for at least 20 minutes, followed by 3 mM glucose perfusion for at least 5 minutes, KCl simulation to assess cell response to potassium for 5 minutes, then wrapped up with 3 mM glucose back for 5 minutes.

The recording environment temperature was maintained at 37° C by using either a thermostat (E5CSV, OMRON) or temperature controller unit (TRZ 3700, Carl Zeiss) under the integrated board with the electrode and microfluidic device, with a temperature probe to ensure the 37° C on the heat pad interfacing the device as shown in Figure 3.3.1. The medium was perfused at a 70 $\mu\text{l}/\text{minute}$ flow rate to replicate the blood vascularisation flow rate within the channels, paying attention to generations of signal distortion or deviation after introducing the fluidic flow.

3.3.4 Signal Processing Algorithms

The recorded electric potential signals were processed offline with several filter modules and protocols on Python, for instance, with the *filtfilt* and *fft* modules from

Figure 3.3.1: Experiment setup and equipment.

SciPy library, after being processed by the previous analog blocks. The algorithm did not include any processing for peak detection considering the project stage, which still aims for sufficient recording results first; therefore, no measurement decision-making feature was embedded in the algorithm.

The frequency response of the recorded signals was initially performed to observe their frequency distribution. As 50 Hz noise from the power line and its harmonics would be the most significant interference, a digital IIR notch filter on 50 Hz was implemented with a Q factor of 30, inferred by optimising the digital filter frequency response to achieve steep roll-off slope representing narrow filter bandwidth and highest interference attenuation.

Further processing was then divided into two distinct frequency bands, each for slow potential and action potential filter. Each filter frequency response was observed before implementation to verify the filter bandwidth output. The slow potential filter was applied with a third order Butterworth filter with 0.24 Hz and 4 Hz cutoff frequency for the HPF and LPF, respectively. Meanwhile, the action potential filter was applied with a sixth order Butterworth filter with 20 Hz and 499 Hz cutoff frequencies for the HPF and LPF, respectively.

Chapter 4

Results and Analysis

The chapter will cover the results of the fabrication along with encountered challenges, results on different subsystem integration and assembly, and finally, the performance of both microfluidic trapping and electrophysiology recording with islets. Initial findings from the signals and the interpretation will be described, along with possible explanations and suggestions to improve them further.

4.1 Pilot Trials and Prototyping

The pilot trials focused on improving several technical aspects to establish the optimised experiment setup, such as finding strategies for microbeads and islet loading to prevent sedimentation, setting up the medium change in channels in the fluidic system with precise control, observing the trapping behavior with the U-cup system, and pursuing trials with culture in the microfluidics.

4.1.1 Microbeads and Islets Loading Optimisation

Initially, fluid control was achieved using a simplified setup of a syringe pump and tubing at the inlet to pump the fluid toward the outlet. However, sedimentation and attachment of the beads and islets in the syringe made it difficult to deliver them into the microfluidic system. Additionally, the tubing used in the system increased the chances of introducing bubbles, especially when switching between different mediums at the inlet.

Introducing microbeads or islets within a solution to the microfluidic system has

challenges from sedimentation occurring over time. As the microbead's and islets' behavior in their medium suspension tends to sediment due to gravity, one way to keep them uniformly distributed is by periodically mixing or moving them. To counteract the issue, some methods of resuspension has been considered, including an approach of introducing manual agitation with a magnetic stirrer and external magnet, rotating the whole syringe with a motorised system, increasing the particle concentration to match the density, or even replacing the medium to match the viscosity and extend the sedimentation period. [106]

However, those approaches involve an over-engineering approach to this trivial issue and adding more constraint that is already limited to begin with. The mechanism of mixing the suspension in the syringe also does not necessarily solve the issue immediately, as if the platform still involves a tubing connection, the particles in the suspension could still get sedimented along the way, lowering the yield of the actual particles that enter the microfluidic channels.

Therefore, to address those issues, the pumping system was replaced by a syringe pump set at the outlet, introducing negative pressure instead of positive pressure from the inlet to withdraw the medium, while an 18 gauge blunt tip was used as the pre-inlet reservoir. The strategy resolves the concerns on particle sedimentation by utilizing their characteristics to be sedimented towards the gravity force and provides more practicality to change the medium in the experiment. Furthermore, islet retrieval was possible after on-chip measurements by introducing positive pressure from the outlet, which allows for further off-chip downstream evaluation.

As shown in Figure 4.1.1, an 18-gauge blunt tip was initially used as the on-chip reservoir at the inlet, with medium added discretely during the experiment. Despite successful trapping, the loading mechanism has a huge drawback of requiring close monitoring of the inlet reservoir volume to prevent drying and major bubble issues. An open PDMS reservoir well was then created to establish a larger reservoir volume as the second improvement, instead of the 18 gauge blunt tip, to provide a longer time window in the experiment. The on-chip reservoir is introduced with a concave curvature at the bottom to direct the sedimentation direction towards the inlet instead. The flow from the negative pressure introduced at the outlet would direct the particles in the medium heading up from the reservoir to the fluidic channel.

However, neither of them allows for automatic medium perfusion, which becomes

Figure 4.1.1: Development of reservoir system to avoid sedimentation and bubble issues.

an issue where the reservoir must be filled with medium with attention towards the emptied reservoir. To make the flow continuously run with media flow from the other tubing end automatically, the reservoir system has to be tightly closed to make a closed system, letting the negative pressure take out the medium instead. Therefore, a 1.5 mL centrifuge tube with the bottom end replaced by concave end PDMS was finally utilized as the latest on-chip reservoir in the system.

Concave reservoir end behaves as a funnel for the islets to enter microfluidic channel

Figure 4.1.2: Concave reservoir end supporting islets delivery into the microfluidic channel, with the third version (left) and the first version (right) reservoir.

The 1.5 mL centrifuge tube reservoir allows automatic medium acquisition from tubing connected to a syringe while still allowing manual loading of islets to the reservoir from the tube cap. When the closed fluidic state has been established with the reservoir, access during islet loading might be provided by stopping the syringe pump and clamping both the inlet and outlet tubing to ensure there is no backflow pushing the fluid level when the reservoir cap is opened. The reservoir also serves the additional feature of preventing bubbles from the inlet from going inside the fluidic channel. Figure 4.1.2 shows a preview of the concave reservoir end.

4.1.2 Microbeads and Islets Trapping Results

The flow along the microfluidic channel was controlled by negative pressure through a syringe pump-connected tubing at the outlet for fluidic delivery and islets

immobilisation. Negative pressure flow from the outlet along the channel wall generates side sheath flow, which attracts the incoming islets to be trapped on the vacant trapping side. An optimum flow rate at $70 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ was applied to ensure that the particle samples had enough time to be trapped towards the trapping site while also allowing for visible monitoring of the process with fast enough loading time.

Trials on trapping microbeads and islets have been performed, with the microfluidics system exhibiting the ability to trap and release each individual particle by merely changing the flow direction. Figure 4.1.3 presents hydrodynamically trapped beads and islets. The immobilisation of the microbeads and islets into the trapping site is closely related to their dimension. Particles larger than the U-cup trapping site opening, such as multiple attached islets or excessive flow rate, might result in trapping failures.

The beads and islets are well-trapped for at least 60 minutes by the U-cup trapping site once they are settled, even without negative pressure being introduced in the system. The setup enables the successful loading and trapping of both microbeads and islets in the device. The trapping mechanism exhibits low sensitivity of the trapped particles to flow fluctuations in the same flow direction, such as changes in medium and flow rates, as long as no excessive flow rates (for instance, $1 \text{ mL}/\text{minute}$) were introduced to the channel. Additionally, microbeads or islets recovery after trapping was achieved by implementing backflow from the outlet to the inlet reservoir.

Figure 4.1.3: Trapped microbeads and islets during pilot trials.

A closed microfluidics system developed in the project answers the concern regarding exposure to contamination from the open air. To further examine this, a long-term culture test was performed by trapping the islets in the fluidic system with Matrigel and RPMI 1640 medium supply in the reservoir for 27 days. Matrigel was used in the culture experiment instead of the fluidic system to maintain the islet position, as the syringe pump utilized in the project does not allow constant flow to be given over a long period of time. Previews of the trapped islets on day 1 and day 4 are shown in Figure 4.1.4.

Figure 4.1.4: Trapped islets on day 1 (top) and day 4 (bottom) with Matrigel delivered to the microfluidic channel.

Matrigel filling in the microfluidic channel represents the system's fluidic delivery pathway. The visual of the main channel trace on day 1 shows that the Matrigel is being sent to the second row through the second U-cup trapping site at the first row instead of being perfused through the main channel. This might indicate that the respective trap site was not behaving appropriately, perhaps due to non-optimised PDMS bonding at the particular spot. It explains why the region exhibited low resistance, which is preferred by the fluidic direction to go through the specific path instead of the main channel. Due to the speculated improper bonding at the site, the serpentine channel at the first row becomes a blind spot area instead. Furthermore, the Matrigel traces on the fourth-day image at the aperture end of the other trapping site region also reveal the fluidic delivery dynamic in the system. A detailed preview of each of the islet conditions on day 4 is presented in Figure 4.1.5.

Figure 4.1.5: Detailed visuals of each trapped islet on day 4 with Matrigel delivered to the microfluidic channel.

The culture test with Matrigel was prolonged until 27 days. The visual comparison of some trapped islets’ morphology changes throughout the experiments can be seen in Figure 4.1.6, while all trapped islets comparison of day 4 to day 27 is visible in Figure fig:matrigelcultureal4and27.

Day 1	Day 4	Day 5	Day 27

Figure 4.1.6: Visuals of some trapped islets on days 1, 4, 5, and 27 with Matrigel delivered to the microfluidic channel.

Up to day 5, no contrast morphology nor size alteration was observed from the trapped islets. However, on day 27, some islets present necrotic cells in the nucleic region with few disintegrated cells on the outer periphery of the islets. Furthermore, one of the islets, which had already started disintegrating on day 4, became totally disintegrated on day 27. This is not a surprising result, although the medium was pumped into the channel daily, the perfusion of vascularization medium from the inlet reservoir was not provided continuously. Disintegrated cells often indicate some cell death that is

likely to occur from loosening membrane integrity, causing them to be detached from the intact islets. Further investigation on the islets' viability might be performed by employing live/dead viability stains such as trypan blue following a similar experiment. However, it was not regarded as the main objective of this trial.

Figure 4.1.7: Visuals of trapped islets on days 1 and 27 with Matrigel delivered to the microfluidic channel.

From the experiment, it was then stipulated that no contamination occurred within the system, as the overall inspection inside the channel also did not present signs of bacterial or fungal contamination, proving that the closed system provided a sterile environment within the microfluidics and supporting the subsequent experiments with the islet. Moreover, as the hydrodynamic trapping in the microfluidics is inferred viable to maintain the islets' position, the trial was then pursued to integrate the microfluidic system with existing electrodes in the laboratory and optimise their integration protocols.

To test proper islet placement on the developed electrode later on, an initial proof-of-concept was performed to bond the microfluidic chip with a 200 μm wide planar gold electrode. The electrode functionality was not the main aspect to be examined in this phase, but more on deciding the electrode placement within the hydrodynamic trapping system. Figure 4.1.8 presents how the islet is typically trapped at the trapping site, with a tendency to be closer towards the aperture opening but not to the end depth part. The trapping behavior was then used as the basis to set the alignment position

between the designed microelectrodes array and the microfluidics.

Figure 4.1.8: Designed electrode alignment with the microfluidic trapping site according to trapped islet placement behaviour from prior trials.

4.2 Iterated Development

4.2.1 Microelectrode Fabrication Challenges

In the iteration development phase, the microfluidic was initially considered to be replaced by SU-8 instead of PDMS to allow their precise alignment and bonding with the mask aligner in the cleanroom. However, fabricating a tall SU-8 with $300\ \mu\text{m}$ height is considered tricky and time-consuming, especially considering the available SU-8 in the laboratory is mostly dedicated to less than $100\ \mu\text{m}$ height.

During passivated electrode fabrication, gold deposition on the glass substrate encountered no issue, while some issues on the SU-8 passivation layer to the electrode were encountered, with non-polymerised SU-8 coming off and adhering non-uniformly. The thickness of the fabricated SU-8 layer correlates with the dispensed volume in the spin coating process, the exposure dose, and the heat treatment process following the recommendation on the manufacturer's datasheet. The protocols to achieve $2\ \mu\text{m}$ thick of SU-8 2002 based on the recommended parameters were followed thoroughly and accordingly, but the issues still occur.

It was suspected that the uncured SU-8 was due to insufficient exposure dose since the manufacturer's recommendation was based on fabrication with a silicon substrate, meanwhile, glass substrates were used instead in this case. To solve the problem, gold-patterned glass substrates were ensured to be clean from contaminants by treating

them in the oxygen plasma under 140 ml/minute oxygen flow with 150 W power for 10 minutes and dehydrated in the 150^o C oven overnight. The wafers were also treated with HMDS as an SU-8 adhesion promoter on the metal-coated glass substrate. As a negative photoresist, SU-8 crosslink behavior has the best absorption rate of 365 nm UV light. Therefore, instead of using the default 405 nm wavelength from the mask aligner, a 365 I-line filter was used to optimize the exposure.

Furthermore, several iterations of the exposure time were done to optimise the exposure dose. According to the SU-8 2002 datasheet, the recommended exposure energy for 2 μm thickness is 80 mJ/cm², which then increased to 1.5 \times into 120 mJ/cm² dose to account for their exposure on glass instead of silicon wafers. As the MA6/BA6 aligner utilised 350 W mercury lamp with 20 mW/cm² light intensity, and dose in mJ/cm² refers to the light intensity multiplied with the exposure time in second, theoretically, 120 mJ/cm² dose might be achieved by exposing the SU-8 film for 6 seconds.

However, the increased dose still resulted in undercured SU-8; therefore, the dose was finally further doubled to 240 mJ/cm² from the iteration trials with varying exposure time from 12-25 seconds. It was then found that to achieve a strongly adhering SU-8 layer, 25 seconds of exposure time with the I-line filter is needed. This result might come from reduced mercury light intensity reduction that is not exactly 20 mW/cm² after applying the I-line filter, combined with the sight of bubbles and imperfect fidelity on the photomask indicating a need for increased exposure dose. The imperfection on the photomask might scatter or diffract the light in the exposure step, leading to uneven exposure and unbalanced crosslinking. A much higher exposure dose has solved this issue temporarily; however, further examination of SU-8 crosslinking on the substrate should be done more thoroughly. Another solution that might avoid the issue in the first place is using a photomask with higher quality since the PET film photomask has much lower reliability than chrome glass photomask, which is the common standard in microfabrication.

4.2.2 Microfluidic Fabrication and Integration Results

The iterated silicon wafer mold template for microfluidics soft-lithography has some issues with reverse taper profiles observed, indicating failure to achieve high-aspect-ratio structures with anisotropic etch profiles. It is plausible that it results from

overetched silicon wafers, where the etch profile depth during assessment with profilometer exhibits a depth ranging between 320-400 μm , indicating non-uniform etch as well. Figure 4.2.1 includes the comparison of the silicon mold to the patterned PDMS. Different focal points to the base and the surface present some stuck PDMS left out on the silicon wafer, with a tapering angle and rounded square on the surface, which was supposed to be a sharp angle and well-defined wide square instead. It is not so problematic for the main channel patterning, yet it is a significant issue on the trapping sites, particularly those with double and triple U-cup trap site configurations. Detailed representation of the etch profile is illustrated in Figure 4.2.2.

Figure 4.2.1: Overview on silicon wafer mold templates.

Figure 4.2.2: Expected and suspected etch profile on the silicon wafer mold template.

The reverse taper etch profile on the structures clearly explains why some of the poured PDMS got trapped inside the cavity and cannot be removed altogether with the whole structure, resulting in the patterned PDMS not having the best structural fidelity. The design replication issues become another factor as to why the trapping behavior on the latest microfluidic design was not as reliable as the other microfluidics with the previous silicon mold template, even though they have the exact same design other than the number of trapping site arrays in the device. The undesired etch profile then causes most of the recently fabricated mold templates of double and triple U-cup trap sites to be unusable.

Despite how the double and triple mold structures were unsuccessfully replicated with high fidelity from unpeeled structures on the silicon mold, the mold template with single U-cup trap sites is still deliverable. The single trap site configuration with tapering angles has similarities to those of double and triple U-cup trap sites on the previous silicon mold template. A comparison of the recent silicon mold template to the previous one is highlighted in Figure 4.2.3. It seems that the peeling failure mostly occurred to the dimensionally smaller structures, such as the trapping aperture structure, at the double and triple U-cup, which are more affected in the event of overetch. The single U-cup was made without such an issue, perhaps as no small structure is involved in the layout.

Figure 4.2.3: Comparison of silicon wafer mold templates with bad (left, horizontal) and good (right, vertical) fidelity.

Regardless of the imperfect structure fidelity, the single U-cup trap site configuration was still bondable to the microelectrodes array. In Figure 4.2.4, the right figure presents the successfully bonded PDMS and APTES modification on the surface, with a tight bond area on the larger surface region and the slightly unbonded surface area close to the trap sites. Similar profiles were also observable in microfluidic devices fabricated from the previous silicon mold template. The less tight bond interaction on the trapping sites explains why some of the microbeads or islets during the pilot trials seemed to be pushed underneath the aperture opening at the end of the trap sites. The right side of Figure 4.2.4 shows the bonding results with SU-8 insulated electrode without surface modification with APTES and how the bonded PDMS to the electrode with failed trap site formation from bad structural fidelity on double trap sites configuration.

Figure 4.2.4: PDMS structural fidelity on the bonded device.

To further show how the bonding quality varies between different surface treatments, Figure 4.2.5, 4.2.6, 4.2.7, and 4.2.8 respectively shows the bonding results on air plasma treatment, oxygen plasma treatment, air plasma and APTES (both phases), and air plasma and vapor phase APTES. The vapor phase APTES bonding is demonstrated as less reliable compared to the liquid phase APTES silanisation. The visual of the bonded PDMS and glass with APTES on the vapor phase looked okay initially, but once the assembly with silver epoxy was performed to connect the device to the circuit connector board, the structure immediately came off.

Figure 4.2.5: Results on PDMS bonding with air plasma.

Figure 4.2.6: Results on PDMS bonding with oxygen plasma.

Figure 4.2.7: Results on PDMS bonding with air plasma and APTES (both phases).

Figure 4.2.8: Results on PDMS bonding with liquid phase APTES

Some of the assembly processes were done at the MST laboratory, where only air plasma is available, instead of oxygen plasma at the Scilifelab facility. Oxygen plasma treatment presents a more effective bonding from the more reactive oxygen species produced on the treated surface.

Surface-activated PDMS must be in contact immediately after being oxidized in the plasma to avoid their hydrophobic recovery. This factor becomes the main challenge in manual alignment and bonding, which exposes them to a longer time following the plasma treatment. Additionally, bonding quality is also affected by surface cleanliness. Surface contaminants must be avoided to ensure bonding surface flatness, where exposure to open air during the manual alignment might also introduce dust or other contaminants.

Following the optimised protocols, the PDMS microfluidic chip was managed to be bonded on top of the electrodes, and their bonding quality was analysed through a leakage test by filling the channel with water and applying some pressure through a hand-controlled syringe from both the inlet and outlet. In the event of failed bonding, an attempt to seal the leakage points with uncured PDMS was made, but it was considered impractical as it risks the uncured PDMS going inside the channel

cavities.

4.2.3 Hardware Subsystem Integration

The connection between the electrodes and the connector board was made by conductive silver epoxy. Silver epoxy conductivity was obviously not as good as wire bonding; however, wire bonding could not possibly be carried out during the fabrication stage of the project, which occurred during the summer period. Previews of the integrated device on the connector board and the finalised platform are shown in Figure 4.2.9 and Figure 4.2.10.

Figure 4.2.9: Wire-bonded device on pilot trials (left) and silver epoxy on latest device (right).

Figure 4.2.10: Overview of the finalised platform.

The connections between the electrodes and the connector boards were ensured by testing their connectivity via a hand-held multimeter. Based on several trials, when the silver epoxy was not entirely cured or an insufficient amount of the conductive

silver was applied, the contact pad of the electrodes and the connector board would not have any electrical connection. When all the aimed connections have been ensured to be made properly, the integrated device is ready to be used in a plug-and-play format with the front-end electronics.

4.3 System Evaluation

4.3.1 Hydrodynamic Trapping Performance

Prior to the experiment, the microfluidic channel has to be wetted and ensured that there is no bubble disrupting the trapping site and recording area. In the pilot trials, the experiment was originally initiated by perfusing absolute ethanol inside the fluidic channel for wetting. However, it was found that the wetting process with ethanol did not significantly result in bubble-free perfusion and trapping. Additionally, some bubbles were observed to be generated from beneath the trapping site, not coming from the outer part of the system. The experiment protocols were then improvised by immediately perfusing the microfluidics channel with culture medium or physiological buffer for 5 minutes, skipping over the ethanol wetting. The generated bubbles were then simply dismissed by introducing additional pressure from both the inlet and outlet to eliminate the bubbles. Snippets of trapped islets and their positions on 30 μm and 50 μm diameter electrodes at the trapping sites are shown in Figure 4.3.1 and Figure 4.3.2.

Figure 4.3.1: Trapped islets on 30 μm and 50 μm diameter recording electrodes.

The trapped islets have been positioned right on top of the recording electrodes, with the islets completely covering the electrode surface. Observation of the system through an inverted microscope shows that when the focal point on the electrode surface was established during experiments, the trapped islets became visible at the same focal point where the electrode and PDMS surface level were observed. Physical contact

Figure 4.3.2: Trapped islets inside the integrated device.

between the islet and electrode was ensured by observing the device with an inverted microscope and changing the objective focus accordingly. When the islet surface was at the same focus level as the electrode, they were assumed to be on the same height level, which indicated that physical contact between them was achieved.

4.3.2 Front-end Electronics Characterisation

Prior to electrophysiology recording experiments, the front-end electronics were checked by introducing a sinusoidal signal from a signal generator to verify the expected output. If the circuit behaves properly, it is supposed to send the output signal within the desired frequency range and proper signal amplification.

The first electronics board in pilot trials was observed to withdraw some current from the power supply, which indicates that the circuit was connected properly. However, the electrical recording presented a highly fluctuating response and was immensely susceptible even to a slight cable movement. A simulation of the utilised circuitry was then performed on LTspice, and it was found that no intended signal behavior was observed. The front-end electronics block was then redesigned by defining the design requirement in more detail to acquire the desired signals with a more stable baseline.

The redesigned front-end circuitry consists of several signal conditioning blocks, the IA,

HPF, and LPF blocks, to ensure the low-amplitude signals are amplified into sufficient voltage levels detectable by the oscilloscope without too much distortion. The overall schematic design has been shown in the previous chapter in Figure 3.1.9.

Figure 4.3.3: Implemented IA block design.

Figure 4.3.4: Simulation of analog high-pass and low-pass filter and implemented design.

The instrumentation amplifier was implemented with schematic design as referred to in Figure 4.3.3. With the designed passive components value, the IA block should produce $\pm 10\times$ voltage gain equivalent to $\pm 20 \text{ dB}$ gain with HPF function -3 dB point at $\pm 1.59 \text{ Hz}$. Meanwhile, the subsequent design of the analog filters are shown in Figure 4.3.4, with finalised component values for each HPF and LPF block represented in Figure 4.3.5 and Figure 4.3.6.

One of the capacitor's values in the HPF block was implemented with a different

Figure 4.3.5: HPF block schematic design and passive components values.

tolerance level due to availability issues from the PCB manufacturer, but it is expected to present a close to no issue on the overall block function. However, a more significant design fault was made on the LPF block, where a different tolerance level of the capacitor was also chosen, combined with two mistakenly applied resistor values. The design fault mistake happened as some part of the LPF block design was copied from the HPF schematic drawing, but the resistor values have not been checked thoroughly.

Figure 4.3.6: LPF block schematic design and passive components values.

Based on the calculation, the HPF block should produce ±10× voltage gain equivalent to ±20 dB gain with -3 dB point at ±99 mHz, and the LPF block should generate ±89× voltage gain or ±39 dB gain with -3 dB point at ±930 Hz. Combined with previous amplification at the IA block, the output of the designed front-end electronics should result in ±1100× voltage gain equivalent to ±60 dB. Although the design fault in the LPF block does not necessarily affect the filter bandwidth, the total gain is impacted by the fault resistors value, where the block only adds ±2× voltage gain equivalent to ±6 dB instead of ±10× voltage gain or ±20 dB gain. One-fifth of the gain produced in the LPF block then results in the total gain of ±220× voltage gain or ±46.8 dB gain.

To prove the hypothesis, simulation on both the calculated design and the implemented

design was done on LTspice with a focus on both the frequency response and the voltage output from sinusoidal wave input with $100 \mu\text{V}_{\text{pp}}$ amplitude at 100 Hz frequency. The simulation results are shown in Figure Figure 4.3.7 and Figure 4.3.8.

Figure 4.3.7: Simulation of frequency response on each block from calculated and implemented design.

In frequency response, the -3 dB point refers to the frequency where the system achieves half the initial power, indicating the implemented filter’s cutoff frequency. The highest magnitude level with a flat band over a certain range of frequencies inferred the magnitude of amplification on the Y-axis and their bandwidth over the X-axis. The comparison between the simulation of the calculated design and the implemented one did not present any differences in IA and HPF block output. Still, it indeed has different results at the LPF block. The frequency bandwidth is still maintained over a similar frequency range. However, the amplitude magnification has a far reduced amount on the implemented design with ± 45 dB gain instead of 60 dB gain.

The simulated voltage response also presents a similar reduced response, where the calculated design was supposed to reach a total output of $\pm 110 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$ amplitude in response to the $100 \mu\text{V}_{\text{pp}}$ input. Yet, the implemented design only reaches up to $\pm 22 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$, which is equivalent to $\pm 220\times$ voltage gain instead of the intended $\pm 1100\times$.

The simulation result on the implemented design at the LPF block output, representing the overall combined front-end electronics response, was then compared to real

Figure 4.3.8: Simulation of output voltage response from calculated and implemented design.

measurements with the board on their frequency response and voltage response, as shown in Figure 4.3.9 and Figure 4.3.10. According to both simulation and measured frequency responses, the front-end electronics circuitry managed to reach $\pm 45 \text{ dB}$ gain, with flat band gain over 30 dB at the aimed signal bandwidth of 0.1 Hz to 3 kHz. Although the filter presents a sufficient result, the amplification might cause concerns about capturing the real extracellular islet voltage signals.

Voltage response assessment with previously input amplitude around $100 \mu\text{V}_{\text{pp}}$ would be beneficial in this case, but the signal generator available in the project only allows the lowest voltage of $10 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$ to be delivered. Therefore, the voltage response check was done with input of $10 \text{ mV}_{\text{pp}}$ at 100 Hz for both the simulation and real measurement of the board. Although the design fault at the LPF block causes the front-end electronics not to meet the intended design requirement, the simulated and acquired measurement results exhibit similar output voltage responses. It shows that while the implementation was not successfully done accordingly, the design has been done thoroughly, as the solution would simply be to revise the design fault to match the simulated response.

Figure 4.3.9: Comparison of simulated and measured frequency response from the implemented front-end electronics design.

For future improvement, the electrode-islets interface may actually be modelled into certain capacitors and resistor combination values representing the aimed interference to simulate the electronics system in a more accurate way. Another improvement on measurement verification might also be made by using a voltage divider network connected to the signal generator to make the input signal in the microvolt range and simulate the real signal in a more representative amplitude.

4.3.3 Preliminary Electrophysiology Recording Results

The main device, which consists of a microfluidic-integrated microelectrodes array, was utilised to assess islet response following dynamic exposure of different stimuli toward the islets. To support the on-chip electrical recording experiments, the integrated device was placed on top of a temperature controller, and front-end electronics connected to the digital oscilloscope were used as the signal acquisition unit block. Live preview of the electrical response was possible to be done through the oscilloscope-connected PC, with the native app provided by the oscilloscope. However, thorough data analysis has to be done offline following the signal acquisition, as the oscilloscope native app does not provide a fully-customised digital function with high flexibility. A better interpretation of signals would only be possible once offline digital signal processing is performed to rule out the noise and artifacts by filtering.

Although the front-end electronics block has three input and output channels, the platform can only record the electrical activities from two electrode channels simultaneously due to the limitation on the number of available oscilloscope input

Figure 4.3.10: Comparison of simulated and measured output voltage response from the implemented front-end electronics design.

channels. The recording setup forward the acquired signals from the electrodes to be amplified and filtered on the front-end electronics and digitised at a sampling rate of 2 kHz on the oscilloscope.

The FPGA-based oscilloscope (Moku:Go, Liquid Instruments) has two input and output channels ranging up to 20 MHz analog bandwidth and 125 kHz sampling frequency. The oscilloscope presents a ± 5 V input voltage range and 12-bit ADC resolution, which is equivalent to a 10 V total voltage range divided into 4096 steps or 2 mV resolution. Assuming that the signals from islets have ± 100 μ V amplitude, for instance, it was supposed to be amplified into ± 110 mV range after being amplified on the front-end electronics with $\pm 1100\times$ voltage gain. However, with the implemented design achieving only $\pm 220\times$ voltage gain, the ± 100 μ V signals from the islet would only be amplified into ± 22 mV. As the oscilloscope has a 2 mV voltage resolution, the lowest amplitude from the electrode to be detectable is only ± 9 μ V.

Raw signals acquired from the measurement without further digital signal conditioning were totally uninterpretable. Each of the channels represents a different individual recording electrode in the system, with Figure 4.3.11

showing the snippet from early experiments without established protocols and Figure 4.3.12 representing the result from the latest experiment. The differences in them are improved shielding and disconnecting the oscilloscope-connected PC from the power line. In more detail, the comparison between the frequency response on the raw signals and the notch-filtered signals are completely different in the time domain, with the frequency response distribution still exhibiting a similar pattern other than at 50 Hz and its harmonics where the notch filter intended to impact them.

Figure 4.3.11: Comparison of raw signals to notch-filtered signals and their respective frequency response from one of the early experiments.

Figure 4.3.12: Comparison of raw signals to notch-filtered signals and their respective frequency response from one of the latest experiments.

The digital IIR notch filter on 50 Hz was implemented with a Q factor of 30, inferred by their frequency response to achieve a steep roll-off slope representing narrow filter bandwidth and highest interference attenuation. Similar assessments to apply the bandpass filter for AP and SP signal bandwidth are also performed, with examples of their response shown in Figure 4.3.13.

Trials on in vitro electrophysiology recording with islets have been performed in 9 different experiments with 7 separated devices, including those with unpassivated

Figure 4.3.13: Examples of implemented digital filter response.

electrodes bonded to PDMS with oxygen plasma, unpassivated electrodes bonded to PDMS with air plasma, and passivated electrodes bonded to PDMS with APTES surface modification. Among those experiments, the most promising result was shown by the device without SU-8 passivation bonded to PDMS through oxygen plasma. A snippet of acquired signals from this specific device is shown in Figure 4.3.14 and 4.3.15

Figure 4.3.14: Snippet of signals filtered on 50 Hz notch filter, AP region bandpass filter, and AP region bandpass filter.

Although some peaks with increased frequency and silence periods in between their bursts were observed during 11 mM glucose stimulation, which is not observable in 3

Figure 4.3.15: Snippet of signals filtered on 50 Hz notch filter, AP region bandpass filter, and AP region bandpass filter.

mM glucose, it might be too early to conclude that the signals are indeed coming from the islet. It is quite challenging to make the result repeatable with different islets, even on the same device and recording electrodes. The measurement was conducted under fully static conditions, as no disturbance to cable movement or other interference was made where the peaks were observed to exclude possibilities of the peaks coming from external factors.

From the visual inspection with an inverted microscope, it is plausible to assume that the islets have physical contact with the electrode. Therefore, the inconsistency of recording results is assumed not to happen from insufficient contact between the islets and electrodes.

To further ensure that the inability to record the signal properly is not coming from incompatibility with the microfluidic trapping system supporting proper islet-electrode contact, a recording trial with a micromanipulator (Eppendorf 5170) to hold the islet and place them directly on one of the recording electrodes was performed to verify the suspicion. Capillary glass with a tip diameter of approximately 100 μm

Figure 4.3.16: Islet placement on top of recording electrode with a micromanipulator.

was interfaced, and gentle negative pressure was applied to hold the islet, as shown in Figure 4.3.16. The recording was done in 11 mM glucose-containing physiological buffer for 30 minutes. The experiment was performed on one of the APTES-modified electrodes with the SU-8 passivation layer, as access into open electrodes was needed without the PDMS fluidic channel covering them.

Figure 4.3.17: Snippet of signals filtered on 50 Hz notch filter, AP region bandpass filter, and AP region bandpass filter.

There was no significant signal observed on all three electrodes connected to the connector board, on which recording of two islets was attempted on those three

electrodes as shown in Figure 4.3.17. It was then presumed that the non-performing system was not due to hydrodynamic trapping incompatibility to place the islets on the electrode. For future development, further characterisation of the electrodes needs to be done to ensure that they are functioning properly, where the most common method is typically done by characterising their impedance profile.

Electrode impedance characterization was about to be conducted with cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at the end of the project, with the experiment setup using one of the microelectrodes as the working electrode (WE), Ag/AgCl electrode with 3 M KCl as the reference electrode (RE), and bare Pt as the counter electrode (CE). All three electrodes emerged in $1\times$ PBS pH 7.4 and integrated altogether in one fluidic system by placing the RE and CE in the microtube reservoir on the inlet and outlet of the microfluidic system. The characterisation trial was planned to sweep the frequency from 100 kHz to 1 Hz, with 30 points per decade at 0 V and 10 mV RMS input for EIS, then 100 mV/s scan speed and -0.8 V to 1 V voltage range for CV. If the electrode impedance reaches more than $2\text{ M}\Omega$, the electrodes would be considered suboptimal. However, the whole experiment was not successfully conducted at the time due to malfunctioning potentiostat on the planned time, and considering the time limitation, it was regarded as an out-of-project objective scope.

For future improvement, electrode impedance characterisation should be the first step after their fabrication to ensure functionality prior to real electrophysiology recording with islets. Alternatively, electrode impedance analysis might be done with the digital oscilloscope, by employing a trans-impedance circuit to measure the ionic resistance in the electrolyte solution. [107] In terms of their performance, low electrode impedance is expected to provide better signal acquisition results. The ideal impedance is supposed to be far below $10\text{ M}\Omega$ to minimise signal artifacts and increase the SNR. [108]

Chapter 5

Discussions and Reflections

The chapter will describe the suggestions for improvements to the platform to achieve the intended results.

5.1 Flaws and Areas for Improvement in Design and Fabrication

While the platform subsystems have been successfully designed and fabricated, their performance in analysing extracellular potentials from islet activity on GSIS stimulation still requires further improvement in development and evaluation. Despite many iterated developments, trials, and experiments taken in the project, the overall performance of the platform is not sufficient enough to produce reliable and repeatable signals. Although the project has defined the requirements of each subsystem and the development of those aims has been pursued, the current state of the developed platform still has a lot of room for improvement. As there are a plethora of variables affecting the end result in the project, it is very crucial to narrow down the possibilities and improve the unfulfilled requirement or performance on those variables.

5.1.1 Microfluidics Subsystem

The smaller channel cross-section on the U-cup trapping site triggers more fluidic resistance. When the opening on the trap is then blocked by the trapped islet, the media would flow through the bypass channel, and the subsequent islets would fill the next trapping site, and so on. One important thing to note based on the observation

of several trials with double or U-cup trap sites is the trapping would be looser if the spacing distance between two or more U-cup trap sites is too short. Therefore, to increase the trapping effectivity and stability in double and triple U-cup trap site configurations, the gap between the traps in one array could be enlarged further.

Gold-patterned glass bonding with PDMS has been reported to have weak fluidic sealing and leakage issues. Depending on their dimension, PDMS might conformally follow a non-flat surface on the substrate at a certain point, yet this is not always the case. An external clamping setup might be applied to maximise their seal; however, it adds internal force and mechanical stress to the device, resulting in another unknown variability in the recording. [109]. Plasma treatment does not improve the formation of covalent bonds between PDMS and gold, unlike the hydroxyl group on PDMS with glass. On the other hand, an additional adhesive layer might create an issue with uniformity and clogging within the channel.

The other improvement in more practical alignment and bonding was highlighted by Tony et al., where PDMS to PDMS bonding following oxygen plasma treatment was performed under a hydraulic press and soft baked at 65° C for 90 minutes to expand the alignment time window. They also attempted to prolong the hydrophilicity state of the treated PDMS surface, avoiding the hydrophobicity recovery by immersing the PDMS in IPA for up to 24 hours and subsequent plasma treatment afterward. [72] The silanol-rich surface was reported to be effectively activated by introducing a low or middle vacuum pressure range in the oxygen plasma. [71] Further exploration on investigating the plasma treatment with different power, pressure, and period might be done to find the optimised parameter in integrating PDMS with gold-coated glass substrates.

5.1.2 Microelectrodes Array Subsystem

The deposited gold on the electrodes might have undergone some physical disturbances during SU-8 insulation layer troubleshooting, where some rip test with tape was performed to ensure the SU-8 crosslink. A similar potential issue on the SU-8 fabrication from the low-quality PET film photomask used in the photolithography process might also reduce the gold electrode's overall performance. If it is possible to use better-quality photomasks, the desired structures would be ensured to have fewer defects and more precise fabrication results, and efficiency in the workflow would be

increased in general by minimising the design and fabrication iterations.

Furthermore, the insulator layer is the main aspect that prevents voltage leakage that might cause electrical interference between channels. If the insulation layer does not have a sufficient thickness and presents a high dielectric constant or has physical damage, parasitic capacitance between the electrolyte on the medium and the electrode might occur. [110]

In high-density MEA, a small electrode diameter is suggested to improve the spatial resolution, combined with multiplexing circuits to improve the recording with reduced parasitic capacitance and resistance. Another study was performed to introduce perforated MEA featuring several micro-sized openings on the substrate and apply negative pressure from the bottom side to control cell positioning on top of the electrode. It might be interesting to combine this approach with the hydrodynamic trap microfluidic to both automatically position the islet and ensure tight contact between the trapped islets and electrodes is established, such as those in the on-chip patch-clamp system.

Considering the hydrodynamic flow pushes the islets laterally to the inner wall of the trapping site, it might be interesting to investigate the overall system performance with a planar electrode embedded on the sidewall instead of the substrate plane. Conformal coating of gold inside a microfluidic wall channel combined with through-PDMS-vias from metal-coated tall SU-8 pillars has been previously reported by employing three fabrication layers to produce 1-mm tall SU-8. The multilayer fabrication involved iterative spin coating and exposure and collective post-exposure bake and development at the final layer. [111] Another approach of embedding electrodes might also be done by injection technique to employ the electrodes on the fluidic sidewall, although the potential issues on alignment and consistent control might be challenging in this case. [112]

5.1.3 Signal Acquisition Subsystem

During the online measurement, the signals are judged based on the signals' morphology and pattern throughout the continuous recording. However, a major pitfall in this procedure is the lack of reliable signals to be qualitatively interpreted in a correct way. The progress on the project could have been more streamlined with access to commercial-grade electrodes or established signal acquisition systems, such as those

from Multi Channel System (MCS) or INTAN Technology. The lack of these resources served as the main constraint affecting the whole project, which required a more generalised development along with the validation and more variables to be considered in the troubleshooting phase, and it would be otherwise more simplified given other circumstances. The commercial signal acquisition system is often complemented with integrated signal processing tools, thus providing the ability to observe the processed results online and in real time. This massive advantage is not achieved yet with the current platform, which still performs the developed signal processing offline. Therefore, the real measurement might feel like the results are blindly acquired without the possibility of giving positive feedback on the protocols to acquire better-conditioned signals.

Despite the abundance of software dedicated to extracellular electrophysiology analysis, compatibility issues with the developed hardware platform in the project necessitate further development of proprietary software supporting data processing and interpretation. During the offline signal processing development phase, an in-depth literature review was also conducted to explore different workflows for signal processing and categorisation, although only a small portion of them have been implemented in the current platform. The investigation was performed, although out of the scope, to gain a perspective on the comparative analysis, assuming the high-quality data for validation would be successfully acquired in the future.

To further elevate their spatial resolution, development is suggested to be directed toward higher electrode density and an equipping acquisition system that supports a high number of multichannel measurements simultaneously. This is where a featured algorithm to distinguish the active, functioning electrodes from the non-functioning ones would become highly necessary when the platform involves many recording electrodes. During the front-end electronics design, the electrode-islets interface may also be modelled into certain capacitor-resistor combination values representing the aimed interference to better characterise the system.

5.2 Evaluation and Refinements of Experimental Protocols

Overall, while the project aims to provide comprehensive development of an extracellular electrophysiology platform for islet functionality assessment, some limitations impact the results and application. The most important aspect is the lack of external validation and proper characterisation of the subsystems. Considering the time and resource availability, the project only involved in-house hardware and software, hiding the flaw in the system's robustness with no external validation with the established recording system to compare the developed platform's performance. Furthermore, only a limited set of parameters were optimized and investigated in the project, which is not sufficient if all the factors affecting the electrophysiology recordings are taken into account.

Limited access to cleanroom facilities restricts further design iterations and fabrication exploration on the electrodes. In addition to design and fabrication challenges, the project also unexpectedly expands beyond the initial scope as it requires developing the electrophysiology recording system to support the extracellular potential measurement. Development towards custom hardware and software is thus mandatory, as access to established signal acquisition systems to perform the measurement was not achievable. While the team has expertise in various areas, specialised knowledge in extracellular potentials in islet activity was gained simultaneously along the progress. It resulted in more time allocation for troubleshooting and significant time investment in the literature review to grasp detailed behavior and signal characteristics.

5.2.1 Evaluation on Microfluidics Performance

Further evaluation and analysis of the microfluidic performance parameters might include quantifying their hydrodynamic trapping efficiency by comparing different particle dimensions and their trapping percentage. The microfluidics system's ability to deliver nutrients and stimulants to the trapped islets might also be ensured by involving experiments with fluidic delivery onto the trapping site by using certain reacting particles to provide exact quantification or colorimetry changes on the delivered amount of medium to the trapping site.

5.2.2 Evaluation on Assessing Islets Functionality and Feasibility

When assessing the cultured islets, visual inspections are performed using a stereomicroscope by paying attention to their morphology. Healthy islets normally exhibit a 50–250 μm diameter spherical shape with high structural integrity and a smooth border around the periphery. They tend to have a darker color compared to the transparent exocrine tissue, but not as dark as those in necrotic cells. Some protrusion from the peripheral surface of islets might indicate decreased viability or indicators of cell death. Larger islets tend to be more prone to hypoxic conditions and necrotic risks, often in the nucleic region, compared to smaller ones. [32] However, it is very important to perform islets viability other than merely visual inspection at certain points to ensure the validity of results, for instance, combining the electrophysiology recording with calcium fluorescence microscopy or live/dead assays, as visual inspection alone does not cover enough information on their underlying functions.

The group of beta cells in the islets are electrically connected, synchronising with each other to the point that the cells communicate whenever some of them detect the local glucose stimulation. The designed hydrodynamic trapping provides the needed medium perfusion to introduce glucose stimulation while still maintaining the islet's function without introducing too much shear stress, as the islet periphery is surrounded by minimal fluid velocity. However, the extracellular physiological buffer used in the experiment could be refined to be more compatible with electrophysiology recording, as the current protocols for synthesizing the buffer were adapted from a protocol originally intended for calcium fluorescence imaging in islet response experiments with glucose stimulation.

The platform also has to be improved to become more robust to external environmental or physiological disturbances. To ensure the recording environment temperature is maintained in the correct range, one of the options might be to embed a microheater as the heating element embedded with a negative temperature coefficient (NTC) thermistor and a voltage divider to measure the temperature. [113] The other alternative is to utilise a Peltier cell with 2 V and 0.7 A power to maintain 37^o C in the recording site. [57]

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Works

The main goal of the project is to deliver a platform to effectively trap the islets on top of the electrode, establishing stable electrical contact and signal reading. Different approaches were performed to optimize the microfluidic trapping protocols on the electrodes, as well as a preliminary assessment of how the typical signal looks like and the interpretation. Each component and subsystem has been investigated thoroughly, from the design rationales and feasibility to the fabrication methods, and the results achieved.

For the microfluidic subsystem, the main goals are to successfully trap and release the islets afterward and to facilitate the medium perfusion. It was found that negative pressure from the outlet combined with closed-system and reservoir on the inlet with open access to load the islets allowed islet trapping and medium perfusion to run autonomously with a programmable syringe pump. Off-chip retrieval after the experiments was also successfully enabled by applying reverse fluidic flow back to the inlet, pushing the islets out of the trap sites, but further tests on their viability following the measurement are suggested to be done. A long-term culture test was also performed, highlighting the reliability of the closed system to maintain sterility and avoid contamination from open air. Hydrodynamic trapping with U-cup trapping sites along the microfluidic channel successfully trapped both microbeads and islets, maintaining their position even without employing negative pressure once they were trapped for more than 60 minutes.

Although some challenges in fabrication and assembly were encountered, both the microfluidics system and microelectrodes array are successfully integrated together

with the connector board to front-end electronics. According to the evaluation of the frequency response, the front-end electronics managed to achieve ± 45 dB amplification with flat band gain of over 30 dB at the aimed signal bandwidth of 0.1 Hz to 3 kHz.

Initial trials on in vitro electrophysiology recording from islets present some promising data, which needs to be further validated by more thorough evaluations. Characterisation of the electrode impedance should be the first aspect to be pursued to ensure an optimised interface with the islets and validate the acquired results. Refinement on some fabrication techniques and recording protocols might also be done to improve the consistency and reliability of the extracellular potential recording with the developed platform.

Despite the setbacks, the developed platform serves as a starting point to support research into the extracellular potential recording of pancreatic islets and other electrogenic cells, with possible integration with other modalities to be incorporated along the platform, for instance, optoelectronics fluorescence measurement. Future research should pursue to expand the groundwork laid in the project to further improve the microfluidic trapping efficiency, microelectrodes array performance, and extend the signal acquisition system features, including adding multiplexing features to the front-end electronics.

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